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Mathematical definitions and fundamental limits:
First results

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the first results on mathematical definitions and fundamental limits in the context of goal-oriented, AI-enabled semantic communication networks for 6G systems. The work focuses on developing novel information-theoretic frameworks and optimization techniques that integrate semantic understanding into communication processes, aiming to improve efficiency and relevance in data exchange. Key contributions include the formalization of semantic information metrics, such as measures from the rate-distortion-perception (RDP) theory, which extend classical rate-distortion models by incorporating perceptual constraints. New approaches using α -divergences are proposed to characterize and optimize semantic interactions. The document also addresses the challenges of semantic language mismatches and introduces methods for bridging these gaps through measurable transformations. Additionally, this deliverable explores cost-performance trade-offs in distributed learning systems and introduces a communication-efficient labelling protocol to enhance machine learning in resource-constrained environments. Strategies for managing dynamic knowledge bases (KBs) using reinforcement learning are outlined, enabling effective organization and retrieval of semantic information. Practical approximation methods for semantic representation and compression are presented, including domain adaptation techniques and deep learning-based approaches for image transmission. These initial results lay a theoretical foundation for advancing the design of AI-driven 6G communication networks, emphasizing the importance of semantic awareness and goal-oriented optimization.

Keywords

6G networks, semantic communication, rate-distortion-perception theory, goal-oriented communication, knowledge base management, α -divergences, semantic information theory, distributed learning, communication efficiency, semantic mismatch, reinforcement learning, deep learning-based compression, domain adaptation, optimization, context-aware decision making, energy-efficient communication, joint source-channel coding, perceptual constraints, semantic queries, dynamic knowledge bases

Contents

1	Introduction	8
2	Semantic information-theoretic metrics, characteristics, and representation of information	9
2.1	Semantic Information-theoretic fundamentals	9
2.1.1	RDP theory via α -divergence	9
2.1.2	RDP theory with side information	13
2.1.3	Measuring semantic language mismatch between source and destination	18
2.2	Cost and performance in control, learning, optimization	20
2.2.1	A Communication-efficient labelling protocol	20
2.2.2	Communication frameworks and related protocols based on semantic queries	23
2.3	Management of semantic KB and model	26
2.3.1	Semantic KB definition	26
2.3.2	Reinforcement learning-based methods for KB management	30
3	Approximation methods	35
3.1	Definition and evaluation of approximate methods	35
3.1.1	Approximating semantic language translator using domain adaptation techniques	35
3.1.2	Image transmission over MIMO channels using DeepJSCC	40
3.2	Topological data representation and semantic extraction	43
3.2.1	Semantic data representation and processing via topological spaces	45
3.2.2	Semantic data compression based on topological dictionary learning	47
4	Conclusion	49

List of Figures

Figure 2-1 Various solutions with the perception constraint fixed to $P = 0.2$.	12
Figure 2-2 Rate-distortion curves for $a = -5, a = -0.5, a = 1.5$, and $a = 3$. The first figure represents $P = 0$ whereas the second $P = 0.7$.	13
Figure 2-3 The system model with side information.	14
Figure 2-4 Semantic mismatch metric	19
Figure 2-5 A learner communicates with a teacher over a constrained communication channel to obtain soft labels for mixed-up batches of unlabeled inputs.	21
Figure 2-6 A learner communicates with a teacher over a constrained communication channel to obtain soft labels for mixed-up batches of unlabelled inputs. Batch size is $B = 4$.	22
Figure 2-7 Random access activated by semantic queries. The figure depicts three phases: (1) a semantic query is broadcasted by the edge server; (2) the devices compute matching scores and filter out irrelevant data; and (3) the devices adopt a random access protocol and transmit their relevant data in an uncoordinated manner.	24
Figure 2-8 Precision and recall for classification at the edge server when considered two different random access protocols activated by semantic queries	25
Figure 2-9 EcoPull, a sustainable IoT image retrieval framework in which two types of TinyML models are installed into IoT devices: i) a behaviour model and ii) an image compressor model	25
Figure 2-10 Energy saving with respect to the Baseline scheme as a function of the number of images per device. We set the number of devices as $K=5$, the number of available slots as $L=5$, and the relevance threshold as $t=0.8$. The baseline scheme is comprised of traditional slotted ALOHA without semantic matching and using (portable network graphics) PNG for image compression.	26
Figure 2-11 Architecture-level illustration of distributed KB in wireless communication systems	27
Figure 2-12 The convergence behaviour of DRL-based KB management strategy (left side); Comparison of our proposed KB management policy with (a) random KB management policy; (b) fixed KB management policy (right side)	35
Figure 3-1 Illustration of the barycentric mapping transporting X_i into a ball of the atom Q_j .	37
Figure 3-2 Information transfer matrix for different class of transformations	38
Figure 3-3 Performance comparison with different ball-radius and different value of SNR (physical channel)	39
Figure 3-4 Image transmission via DeepJSCC	40
Figure 3-5 The pipeline of the DeepJSCC-MIMO scheme	42
Figure 3-6 The architecture of the ViT-based encoder and decoder	42
Figure 3-7 PSNR and LPIPS versus SRNs under bandwidth ratios	43
Figure 3-8 Visual comparison of different schemes on two samples from the Kodak dataset at a bandwidth ratio $R = 1/24$ and different SNRs.	44
Figure 3-9 Examples of topological spaces for semantic data representation [HZP+22]	45
Figure 3-10 NMSE versus representation coefficients, for different strategies	48

Figure 3-11 Example of Semantic Topological Learning.....49

Figure 3-12 NMSE versus representation coefficients, for different compression strategies ...49

List of Tables

Table 2-1 Summary Table of KB Layers and ML Algorithms30

List of Algorithms

Algorithm 2-1 DQN Algorithm for KB Management.....34

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

6G	Sixth-Generation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AKB	Access Knowledge Base
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
BatchBALD	Batch Bayesian Active Learning by Disagreement
BS	Base Station
CC-BAKD	Communication-Constrained Bayesian Active Knowledge Distillation
CSI	Channel state information
CSIR	CSI is available at the receiver
CSIT	CSI is available at the transmitter
DeepJSCC	Deep Joint source and channel coding
DQN	Deep Q-Network
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
GKB	Global Knowledge Base
HiFiC	High-Fidelity Generative Image Compression
IoT	Internet-of-Things
JG-RDPF	Jointly Gaussian Rate-Distortion-Perception Function
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Groups
JSCC	Joint source and channel coding
KB	Knowledge Base
KL	Kullback-Leibler
LKB	Local Knowledge Base
LLM	Large Language Model
MDP	Markov Decision Process
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NMSE	Normalized Mean Square Error
RDP	Rate-Distortion-Perception
RLHF	Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback
SA	Slotted ALOHA
SAA	Slot-Assigned ALOHA
SemCom	Semantic Communication
SEMDAS	Semantic Data Sourcing
SVD	Singular-value decomposition
TinyML	Tiny Machine Learning
UKB	User Knowledge Base

1 Introduction

The 6G of communication networks is expected to represent a profound shift in the design and objectives of wireless systems, transitioning from traditional data-centric paradigms to goal-oriented, semantic-aware frameworks. This evolution reflects the increasing demand for intelligent, context-aware communication systems capable of addressing the complex requirements of modern applications in areas such as learning, control, and optimization. This document introduces foundational mathematical definitions and explores the fundamental limits underpinning goal-oriented SemCom. The document provides a rigorous theoretical basis for understanding and optimizing communication systems where semantic content and contextual relevance take precedence over raw data fidelity.

The 6G-GOALS project [SLS+24] envisions the integration of AI with communication networks to embed meaning, intent, and context into transmitted information. Such an approach shifts the focus from merely transmitting bits efficiently to enabling systems to derive actionable insights aligned with specific goals. This shift introduces new challenges that require an extension of existing communication theories. Traditional metrics like rate and distortion must be augmented to account for the semantic relevance and perceptual quality of information. Furthermore, ensuring seamless communication across heterogeneous systems demands robust methods to quantify and mitigate semantic mismatches in language representations.

To address these challenges, this deliverable focuses on advancing the theoretical framework of SemCom. It introduces RDP theory, which generalizes classical rate-distortion theory by incorporating perceptual constraints to balance the trade-offs among transmission rate, distortion, and perceptual fidelity. Novel measures based on α -divergences are proposed, enabling a more nuanced characterization of semantic interactions and the optimization of communication systems for goal-specific tasks.

Scope and Contributions

This deliverable systematically addresses the key aspects of goal-oriented SemCom through a combination of theoretical advancements and a practical framework that are articulated as follows:

1. **Semantic Information-Theoretic Metrics:** The first section establishes foundational metrics for SemCom, with a focus on the RDP framework. By extending rate-distortion theory to include perceptual quality, this work formalizes the interplay between rate, distortion, and perception. The introduction of α -divergences provides a versatile mathematical tool to model and analyse SemCom across diverse scenarios. These metrics enable a systematic approach to identifying optimal trade-offs in systems where the utility of transmitted information is context-dependent.
2. **Trade-offs in Cost and Performance:** A critical aspect of SemCom is balancing cost and performance, especially in scenarios involving resource-constrained environments. This deliverable investigates frameworks for distributed machine learning and optimization, where semantic queries replace traditional ground-truth labels. A communication-efficient labelling protocol is introduced, enabling systems to acquire semantic insights with minimal data exchange while maintaining task performance. These insights are particularly relevant for applications such as federated learning and IoT networks, where bandwidth and computational resources are limited.
3. **KB Management:** Effective management of distributed KBs is essential for enabling context-aware decision-making in intelligent systems. This deliverable outlines a reinforcement learning-based framework for optimizing KBs. By dynamically organizing and retrieving semantic information, this approach ensures that systems can adapt to evolving objectives and contextual requirements. The proposed strategies enhance the scalability and efficiency of semantic systems in complex and dynamic environments.

4. **Approximation Methods for SemCom:** Practical constraints in SemCom often require approximation techniques to balance computational complexity and performance. In particular, in the finite blocklength regime, it is not possible to achieve Shannon-theoretic limits, e.g., those prescribed by the RDP function. In this deliverable, we instead consider image transmission over a finite blocklength MIMO channel, and explore techniques that can approach the fundamental bounds through a joint design approach. This deliverable then examines methods for semantic data representation, including domain adaptation techniques for semantic translation and deep learning approaches for efficient image transmission over noisy channels. These methods address key challenges in achieving real-time performance while maintaining high semantic fidelity.

Significance

The contributions of this document lay a strong theoretical foundation for the development of semantic-aware communication systems in sixth generation networks. By rigorously defining the interplay between rate, distortion, and perception, and addressing interoperability challenges, this work provides critical insights into the design of goal-oriented communication systems. The proposed frameworks and metrics not only enhance the efficiency of SemCom but also enable systems to prioritize information that is contextually and semantically relevant.

2 Semantic information-theoretic metrics, characteristics, and representation of information

This section is comprised of three subsections. In Subsection 2.1, we give some first results on some semantic information-theoretic fundamentals, whereas in Subsection 2.2 we discuss partial results related to the cost and performance of goal-oriented semantic systems using learning, optimization and the presence of controllers. We conclude this section, with Subsection 2.3 in which we discuss exploiting the semantic KBs as structured repository of information that uses semantic technologies, such as ontologies and reasoning algorithms, to enable machines to understand relationships between data for more intelligent and context-aware decision-making.

2.1 Semantic Information-theoretic fundamentals

In this section, we introduce some fundamental information-theoretic measures and divergences that are relevant in identifying the semantic and goal-oriented aspects of a communication network.

2.1.1 RDP theory via α -divergence

In this subsection, we consider the problem of estimating the RDP function subject to a generic class of divergence constraints modelled by α -divergence.

RDP theory studies rate (R) distortion (D) perception (P) trade-offs and is mathematically quantified by the so-called *RDP function*. This metric is essentially a rate-distortion function with the ability to assess the perceptual quality in addition to the distortion measure. This is defined as [BM19], [M19]

$$\begin{aligned} R(D, P) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min_{p_{\hat{X}|X}} I(X, \hat{X}) \\ E[d(X, \hat{X})] &\leq D \\ D(p_X || p_{\hat{X}}) &\leq P \end{aligned}$$

where X is the source message, \hat{X} is the reconstruction symbol, $d(X, \hat{X})$ is the distortion function, and $D(p_X || p_{\hat{X}})$ is a divergence constraint that measures the discrepancy between the source distribution p_X and the reconstruction distribution $p_{\hat{X}}$. The RDP function provides a fundamental

limit of the triplet (R, D, P) trying to identify coders that may encapsulate a desirable trade-off, depending on the task, between the rate-distortion and perception metrics.

While closed form solutions are generally hard to obtain, it can be proved that the RDP function has the following functional properties [BM19]

1. it is monotonically non-increasing in D and P ;
2. it is convex if the divergence $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ chosen is convex in its second argument.

It is worth pointing out that the rate-distortion curve generally increases when the perceptual quality is constrained to a finite perception level P instead of having an unbounded perception level $P = \infty$. This is because the problem is essentially decoupled from the additional divergence constraint. Additionally, this indicates that good perceptual quality must come at the cost of a higher rate and/or a higher distortion [BM2019].

α -Divergence

Definition: The α -divergence was first proposed by Chernoff [C52] and subsequently, it was thoroughly studied by Amari [A82], [A85]. This class of divergences is comprised of unique canonical divergences that reside at the intersection of the f -divergences and Bregman divergences in a manifold of positive measures. The α -divergence between two (normalized) probability distributions p and q , is defined as [A85]

$$D_{\beta}(p||q) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{4}{1 - \beta^2} \left(1 - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(x)^{\frac{1-\beta^2}{2}} q(x)^{\frac{1+\beta^2}{2}} dx \right)$$

for $\beta \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{\pm 1\}$. The case where $\beta = \pm 1$ can be addressed by taking in the above expression the limit $\lim_{\beta \rightarrow \pm 1}$. Interestingly, $D_{\beta}(p||q)$ and $D_{-\beta}(p||q)$ are dual in the sense that $D_{\beta}(p||q) = D_{-\beta}(q||p)$ is also known as reference duality.

An alternative definition of α -divergence between two normalized probability distributions p and q , is defined as [CR88]

$$D_a(p||q) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{a(a-1)} \left(1 - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(x)^a q(x)^{1-a} dx - 1 \right)$$

for $\alpha \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0, 1\}$. Since $\alpha = \frac{1-\beta}{2}$, the reference duality in this case is expressed as $D_{1-\alpha}(p||q) = D_{\alpha}(p||q)$. In addition, from properties of the metric, it follows that $D_{\alpha}(p||q) \geq 0$ with equality if and only if $p = q$, and that $D_{\alpha}(p||q)$ is not symmetric, i.e., $D_{\alpha}(p||q) \neq D_{\alpha}(q||p)$, except when $\alpha = 0.5$. Moreover, $D_{\alpha}(p||q)$ is convex in both argument p and q .

The role of α : The value of the a parameter may have a significant effect on the resulting approximate distribution q . For $a \leq 0$, the α -divergence enforces q to have low density wherever p has low density (zero-forcing). On the other hand, when $a \geq 1$, the divergence is inclusive, i.e., it enforces $q > 0$ wherever $p > 0$, hence avoiding zero probability density in regions of the space in which p has high density. When $a \in (0, 1)$, the resulting q distribution is intermediate between the two extreme possibilities. In particular, when $a \rightarrow 0$, we should expect that the approximate distribution q is more centred in the main mode of p (mean-seeking). By contrast, when $a \rightarrow 1$, q is expected to cover the target distribution p more and capture more modes (mode-seeking).

Special Cases: Several widely used divergences are actually α -divergences with specific values of α . For instance, when $a \rightarrow 1$ the KL divergence is obtained, when $a \rightarrow 0$ the reverse KL divergence is derived, when $a \rightarrow -1$ the inverse Pearson divergence is given, when $a = 0.5$ the Hellinger distance is obtained, and when $a = 2$ the Pearson divergence results. For $a = 0$, the α -connection [A85] is the Levi-Civita connection under the Fisher-Rao metric. Note that although

the Rényi- α and the Tsallis- α divergences are closely related to the α -divergence, they are not considered special cases of it.

Gaussian case: Under the assumption that p and q belong to the set of Gaussian distributions, i.e., $p = N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ and $q = N(\nu, \rho^2)$, $D_\alpha(p||q)$ can be analytically expressed as

$$D_\alpha(p||q) = \frac{1}{a(a-1)} \left(1 - \frac{\rho^\alpha \sigma^{1-\alpha}}{\sqrt{\alpha \rho^2 + (1-\alpha)\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{\alpha(1-\alpha)(\mu-\nu)^2}{2(\alpha \rho^2 + (1-\alpha)\sigma^2)}} \right).$$

However, the above equation is guaranteed to be real only when $a \in [0,1]$. For $a \notin [0,1]$, additional conditions should be imposed to guarantee that it is a real valued function. For instance, for $a > 1$, the required condition becomes $\sigma^2 < \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \rho^2$, indicating that the variance of p should be smaller than the variance of q multiplied by a constant factor. Clearly, as $a \rightarrow \infty$, this constant factor vanishes, and the condition on the variances simplifies to $\sigma^2 \leq \rho^2$. On the other hand, for $a \rightarrow 1^+$, the constraint disappears in the sense that we simply require $\sigma^2 \leq \infty$ which is always true. For $a < 0$, due to the duality of α -divergence, the conclusions from the case of $a > 1$ can be applied by swapping the roles of σ and ρ . In this case, the constraint shifts to $\sigma^2 > \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \rho^2$. When $a \rightarrow -\infty$, the constraint becomes $\sigma^2 \geq \rho^2$, while for $a \rightarrow 0^-$, the constraint disappears entirely, reducing to $\sigma^2 > 0$.

A Case Study: Jointly Gaussian RDP function subject to α -divergence

In the sequel, we present a case study where we estimate the RDP function subject to an α -divergence assuming jointly Gaussian random variables.

Consider the RDP function problem assuming that the information source is Gaussian distributed, i.e., $X \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$, with $D(p_X || p_{\hat{X}}) = D_a(p_X || p_{\hat{X}})$, and the distortion measure is the MSE metric, i.e., $d(X, \hat{X}) = (X - \hat{X})^2$. Following [SSK24], we can characterise an upper bound to the RDP function for a Gaussian source X by constraining the reconstruction distribution \hat{X} to be jointly Gaussian with X as follows.

Definition 1 [JG-RDPF]: Let $D \geq 0, P \geq 0$. Then, assuming a Gaussian random variable X is JG with a reconstruction variable $\hat{X} \sim q = N(\nu, \rho^2)$, we define the JG-RDPF $R^G(D, P)$ as follows:

$$R^G(D, P) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min_{\nu, \rho^2, p_{X|\hat{X}}} I(X, \hat{X}).$$

$$E[(X - \hat{X})^2] \leq D$$

$$D_a(p||q) \leq P$$

It is important to remark that the following upper bound holds, in general.

Lemma 1 [Upper Bound] [SSS+24]: Let $D \geq 0, P \geq 0$. Then, $R(D, P) \leq R^G(D, P)$.

It should be noted that in the literature, only one case is known for which the upper bound in Lemma 1 is tight. This case corresponds to the reverse KL divergence, i.e., ($a \rightarrow 0$), for which it is proven that the minimizing distribution is itself Gaussian [SSK24].

Without loss of optimality, in Definition 1 we can assume that $\mu = \nu = 0$ since this does not affect the mutual information $I(X, \hat{X})$ from being optimal in terms of the MSE and D_a metrics as stated in the following lemma.

Lemma 2 [Zero-mean JG] [SSS+24]: Let $\Delta = \mu - \nu$. Then, $D_a(p||q)$ has a global minimum at $\Delta = 0$.

The solution of the JG-RDPF in Definition 1 can be greatly facilitated by an in-depth analysis of the perception constraint $D_a(p||q) \leq P$, focusing on the case where it holds with equality. The following lemma characterizes essential aspects of this case.

Lemma 3 [Roots of $D_a(p||q) = P$] [SSS+24]: Assume $P \in [0, P_{\alpha, \max}]$ and let $q = N(0, \sigma^2)$ and $p = N(0, \rho^2)$. Then the constraint $D_a(p||q) = P$ can be expressed as $f(x) = 0$, with

$$f(x) = x^\alpha - aCx - (1 - a)C$$

where $x = \frac{\rho^2}{\sigma^2}$ and $C = (1 - a(1 - a)P)^2$. Furthermore, for all $\alpha \in (-\infty, 0) \cup (0, 1) \cup (1, \infty)$ the equation above has two roots, $r_0 \in [0, x_0]$ and $r_1 \in [x_0, y_0]$ where x_0 is the unique stationary point and $y_0 = (x_0 + \epsilon) - \frac{f(x_0 + \epsilon)}{f'(x_0 + \epsilon)}$ for $\epsilon > 0$.

Lemma 3 demonstrates that, in their respective interval, r_0 and r_1 are the unique roots of the equation in Lemma 3. This property facilitates the application of numerical methods in each interval to estimate the problem such as the bisection method [BFB15].

Equipped with Lemma 3, we state the following major result.

Theorem 1 [Parametric JG-RDPF solution] [SSS+24]: Let X be a scalar Gaussian source $X \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$. Then, the JG-RDPF $R^G(D, P)$ under an MSE distortion and α -divergence perception is achieved by a jointly Gaussian reconstruction $\hat{X} \sim N(0, \rho^2)$ and is given by

$$R^G(D, P) = \begin{cases} \max\left\{\frac{1}{2} \log \frac{\sigma^2}{D}, 0\right\} & \text{if } (D, P) \in S \\ \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{2\rho^2\sigma^2}{\rho^2\sigma^2 - \left(\frac{\rho^2 + \sigma^2 - D}{2}\right)} & \text{if } (D, P) \notin S \end{cases}$$

where

$$\rho^2 = \begin{cases} \sigma^2 - D & \text{if } (D, P) \in S \\ \min\{r_0, r_1\} & \text{if } (D, P) \notin S \end{cases}$$

$$S = \left\{ (D, P) \in \mathbb{R}_+^2 : P > g(D, \sigma) \wedge (\alpha - 1) \left(\left| 1 - \frac{D}{\sigma^2} \right| - \left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha} \right) \right) > 0 \right\}$$

$$g(D, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\alpha(1-\alpha)} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma^{1-\alpha} |\sigma^2 - D|^{\frac{\alpha}{2}}}{\sqrt{\alpha |\sigma^2 - D| + (1-\alpha)\sigma^2}} \right)$$

where r_0 and r_1 are the roots of the equation in Lemma 3.

In the sequel, we corroborate our theoretical results with some numerical studies.

Figure 2-1 Various solutions with the perception constraint fixed to $P = 0.2$.

Figure 2-1 shows the roots of the polynomial introduced in Lemma 3 for different values of α and fixed perception constraint to $P = 0.2$. It is possible to observe that for every value of α , the polynomial has two roots in the disjoint sets defined based on the global extrema.

Figure 2-2 Rate-distortion curves for $\alpha = -5, \alpha = -0.5, \alpha = 1.5,$ and $\alpha = 3$. The first figure represents $P = 0$ whereas the second $P = 0.7$.

Figure 2-2 plots the JG-RDPF curve for varying α values. As expected, for $P = 0$ (perfect perceptual quality), all curves overlap. On the other hand, when $P = 0.7$, the curves diverge from each other, since different α values lead to different perception measures. We notice that as α increases, the curves start to differ more from each other indicating that the perceptual constraint becomes more stringent, leading to higher distortion for the same rate compared to lower α values.

2.1.2 RDP theory with side information

This subsection will unveil how a perception constraint impacts the trade-off between the rate and traditional distortion constraints, typically quantified by a single-letter distortion measure.

In conventional rate-distortion theory, the goal is to enable the decoder to reconstruct a representation of the source signal that is close to the latter for some distortion measure. Shannon characterized the optimal rate-distortion trade-off using the additive distortion measure. Afterward, Wyner and Ziv generalized this result to the case where side information is available at the decoder or both at the encoder and the decoder [WZ76]. This extension allows for more efficient coding by leveraging the correlations between the side information and the main source, effectively reducing the rate without increasing distortion significantly.

Recently, a new neural network-based architecture, e.g., generative deep joint source-channel coding (DeepJSCC), has been emerged [ETDG+23]. Generative DeepJSCC allows the receiver to generate images that resemble the source image semantically, although they may not match perfectly in detail, providing visually pleasing reconstructions even at very low bit rates and low channel quality. However, traditional rate-distortion theory does not account for the perceptual quality of reconstructions. For generative DeepJSCC, there is a notable trade-off between compression rate and perceptual quality. More specifically, small increases in perceptual quality can significantly improve the visual appearance of reconstructions but may also increase the distortion measured by traditional metrics like peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) or MSE.

RDP trade-off with side information framework [HWG24]

Distortion measures like MSE do not fully capture the perceptual quality of reconstructed images or signals. Even if the distortion is low in terms of MSE, the reconstructed image may still appear unrealistic or unnatural to human observers. This is where the perception aspect comes into play, adding a third dimension to the trade-off, alongside rate and distortion. In this context, perception refers to the ability of the reconstructed data to appear visually realistic or statistically similar to the original data distribution.

The RDP trade-off, therefore, aims to strike a balance between Rate (R), Distortion (D), and Perception (P). This is typically measured by a divergence metric that compares the distribution of the reconstructed signal to the source distribution. Metrics like total variation distance, KL divergence, or Wasserstein distance can be used to assess perceptual quality. Perception adds a constraint to ensure that, beyond just minimizing distortion, the output maintains a high level of realism.

Figure 2-3 The system model with side information

Two cases are considered for the study of the RDP trade-off: when the side information Z_n is available only at the decoder or at both the encoder and the decoder as shown in Figure 2-3.

The information-theoretic problem for general alphabets is formulated below. To ensure the existence of a conditional distribution given a joint distribution, it is assumed that all alphabets are Polish spaces¹, encompassing both discrete and real vector spaces.

Definition 1: Given an alphabet χ , a distortion measure is a function $d: \chi \times \chi \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ extending to sequences as

$$d(x^n, y^n) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n d(x_i, y_i)$$

Definition 2: Given two measurable spaces with respective source alphabet χ and Z side-information alphabet, a (n, R, R_c) D-code (resp. E-D-Code) is a privately randomized encoder and decoder couple $(F^{(n)}, G^{(n)})$ consisting of a mapping $F_{M|X^n, J}^{(n)}$ (resp. $F_{M|X^n, Z^n, J}^{(n)}$) from $\chi^n \times [2^{nR_c}]$ (resp. $\chi^n \times Z^n \times [2^{nR_c}]$) to $[2^{nR}]$ and a mapping $G_{Y^n|Z^n, J, M}^{(n)}$ from $Z^n \times [2^{nR_c}] \times [2^{nR}]$ to χ^n .

Definition 3: Given source and side-information alphabets χ and Z and a joint distribution $P_{X, Z}$, a triplet (R, R_c, Δ) is said to be D-achievable (resp. E-D achievable) with near-perfect realism if there exists a sequence of (n, R, R_c) D-codes (resp. E-D-codes) $(F^{(n)}, G^{(n)})_n$ such that

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_P[d(X^n, Y^n)] \leq \Delta,$$

$$\|P_{Y^n} - P_X^{\otimes n}\| \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0,$$

where $P_{X^n, Z^n, J, M, Y^n} = P_{X, Z}^{\otimes n} \cdot P_{[2^{nR_c}]}^U \cdot F_{M|X^n, Z^n, J}^{(n)} \cdot G_{Y^n|Z^n, J, M}^{(n)}$.

¹ The concept of Polish spaces in the context of information theory is used to ensure that certain probabilistic operations, like defining conditional distributions, are well-behaved and mathematically valid. The assumption of Polish spaces guarantees that these operations can be performed on both discrete and continuous alphabets, making it a general and powerful framework for studying information-theoretic problems.

Definition 4: Given a probability space (Ω, \mathcal{B}, P) , an alphabet X , a probability distribution p on X and a distortion measure d , we say that (d, p) is uniformly integrable iff for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a $\tau > 0$ such that

$$\sup_{X, Y, B} E[d(X, Y)1_B] \leq \varepsilon,$$

where X and Y stand for all variables on (Ω, \mathcal{B}) with law $P_X = P_Y = p$ and B represents all events s.t. $P(B) \leq \tau$.

Theorem 5: Given Polish source and side-information alphabets X and Z , a joint distribution $p_{X,Z}$ on $X \times Z$ and a distortion measure d on X such that (d, p_X) is uniformly integrable, then a triplet (R, R_c, Δ) is D -achievable (resp. E - D -achievable) with near-perfect realism if and only if it is D -achievable (resp. E - D -achievable) with perfect realism.

Characterization of RDP trade-off

Prior work [HWG24] on the RDP trade-off without side-information has shown that the availability of common randomness allows to save rate when a perfect or near-perfect realism constraint is imposed. When side information is available at both terminals, it can provide both a second look on the source, as well as additional common randomness independent from the source. This is particularly relevant when no external source of common randomness is available. A characterization of the optimal trade-off is provided in the following theorem.

Theorem 6: Consider a Polish source alphabet X , a finite side-information alphabet Z , a joint distribution $p_{X,Z}$ on $X \times Z$, and a distortion measure d on X such that (d, p_X) is uniformly integrable. Then, the closure of the set A_{E-D} of E - D -achievable triplets (R, R_c, Δ) with perfect or near perfect realism comprises the closure of the following S_{E-D} :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (R, R_c, \Delta): \exists p_{X,Z,V,Y} \in D_{E-D} \text{ s. t.} \\ R \geq I_p(X; V|Z) \\ R + R_c \geq I_p(Y; V|Z) - H_p(Z|Y) \\ \Delta \geq E_p[d(X, Y)] \end{array} \right\},$$

where D_{E-D} is defined as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_{X,Z,V,Y}: (X, Z) \sim p_{X,Z}, \\ p_X = p_Y, \\ X - (Z, V) - Y \end{array} \right\},$$

where the alphabet of V is constrained to be finite.

When the side information is only available at the decoder, we have the following characterization.

Theorem 7: Consider Polish source and side-information alphabets X and Z , a joint distribution $p_{X,Z}$ on $X \times Z$ and a distortion measure d on X such that (d, p_X) is uniformly integrable. Then assuming infinite common randomness, the closure of the set $A_{D,\infty}$ of D -achievable tuples with perfect or near perfect realism is the closure of the following set $S_{D,\infty}$:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (R, \Delta): \exists p_{X,Z,V,Y} \in D_D \text{ s. t.} \\ R \geq I_p(X; V|Z) \\ \infty > I_p(Y; V) \\ \Delta \geq E_p[d(X, Y)] \end{array} \right\}$$

where D_D is defined as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_{X,Z,V,Y}: (X,Z) \sim p_{X,Z}, \quad p_X = p_Y \\ Z - X - V, \quad X - (Z,V) - Y \\ I_p(Z;V) < \infty \end{array} \right\}$$

where the alphabet of V is constrained to be Polish. In addition, in the case of finite common randomness, the closure of the set A_D of D -achievable triplets (R, R_c, Δ) with perfect or near perfect realism comprises the closure of the following S_D :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (R, R_c, \Delta): \exists p_{X,Z,V,Y} \in D_D \text{ s. t.} \\ R \geq I_p(X; V|Z) \\ R + R_c \geq I_p(Y; V) - I_p(Z; V) \\ \Delta \geq E_p[d(X, Y)] \end{array} \right\}.$$

A case study

We study a case where the source and side information form a bi-dimensional Gaussian, then D -achievability is equivalent to E - D -achievability.

Theorem 8: Consider Theorem 7 with infinite common randomness with $d: (x, y) \rightarrow (x, y)^2$

and $p_{X,Z} = N(0, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \eta \\ \eta & 1 \end{pmatrix})$. For any Δ in $(0, 2 - 2\eta]$, and defining $\rho = 1 - \Delta/2$, the infimum of rates with perfect realism is given by:

$$R_D(\Delta) = R_{E-D}(\Delta) = \frac{1}{2} \log\left(\frac{1 - \eta^2}{1 - \rho^2}\right).$$

This can be proved by following two steps:

First, it can be readily seen that $R_D(\Delta) \geq R_{E-D}(\Delta)$. By applying [MKW+11, Proposition 2], the following inequality holds:

$$R_{E-D}(\Delta) \geq \frac{1}{2} \log\left(\frac{1 - \eta^2}{1 - \rho^2}\right),$$

which indicates that

$$R_D(\Delta) \geq \frac{1}{2} \log\left(\frac{1 - \eta^2}{1 - \rho^2}\right),$$

Second, we resort to an upper bound of $R_D(\Delta)$.

Define

$$(Z, X, V) = (\eta\tilde{Z} + \sqrt{1 - \eta^2}\tilde{X}, \tilde{X}, b + \sqrt{1 - b^2}\tilde{V}),$$

where $(\tilde{Z}, \tilde{X}, \tilde{V})$ is a standard Gaussian. Since $\rho \geq \eta$, with

$$b = \sqrt{(\rho^2 - \eta^2)/(1 + \rho^2\eta^2 - 2\rho^2\eta^2)},$$

it can be readily shown that $E[E[X|Z, V]^2] = \rho^2$. Thus, $I_p(X; V|Z) = h(X|Z) - h(X|Z, V) = \frac{1}{2} \log\left(\frac{1 - \eta^2}{1 - \rho^2}\right)$. Define $Y = \rho^{-1}E(X|Z, V)$. One can check that $p_{X,Z,V,Y} \in D_D$, that $E[d(X, Y)] = \Delta$ and that $d(x, p_X)$ is uniformly integrable. Then, by Theorem 7, it follows that

$$R_{E-D}(\Delta) \leq \frac{1}{2} \log\left(\frac{1 - \eta^2}{1 - \rho^2}\right).$$

This thus completes the proof of Theorem 8.

Joint realism

The near-perfect realism constraint in Definition 3 pertains to the realism of the reconstruction. Certain applications involve a more stringent requirement: that the reconstruction and the side information be jointly realistic. This may be the case in video compression, where the side information may be the previous frame. Each notion of achievability in Definition 3 has an analogue with *joint realism*, which is defined by replacing the near-perfect realism constraint by

$$\|P_{Y^n, Z^n} - P_{X, Z}^{\otimes n}\| \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0.$$

Perfect joint realism is defined analogously. Theorem 5 also holds for joint realism. The corresponding RDP trade-off is described in the following theorems, where the superscript (j) stands for joint realism.

Theorem 9: Consider a Polish source alphabet X , a finite side-information alphabet Z , a joint distribution $p_{X,Z}$ on $X \times Z$, and a distortion measure d on X such that (d, p_X) is uniformly integrable. Then, the closure of the set $A_{E-D}^{(j)}$ of E - D -achievable triplets (R, R_c, Δ) with perfect or near perfect joint realism comprises the closure of the following $S_{E-D}^{(j)}$:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (R, R_c, \Delta): \exists p_{X,Z,V,Y} \in D_{E-D}^{(j)} \text{ s. t.} \\ R \geq I_p(X; V|Z) \\ R + R_c \geq I_p(Y; V|Z) \\ \Delta \geq E_p[d(X, Y)] \end{array} \right\},$$

where $D_{E-D}^{(j)}$ is defined as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_{X,Z,V,Y}: (X, Z) \sim p_{X,Z}, \\ p_{Y,Z} = p_{X,Z}, \\ X - (Z, V) - Y \end{array} \right\},$$

where the alphabet of V is constrained to be finite.

Theorem 10: Consider Polish source and side-information alphabets X and Z , a joint distribution $p_{X,Z}$ on $X \times Z$, and a distortion measure d on X such that (d, p_X) is uniformly integrable. Then, the closure of the set $A_D^{(j)}$ of D -achievable triplets (R, R_c, Δ) with perfect or near perfect joint realism comprises the closure of the following $S_D^{(j)}$:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (R, R_c, \Delta): \exists p_{X,Z,V,Y} \in D_D^{(j)} \text{ s. t.} \\ R \geq I_p(X; V|Z) \\ R + R_c \geq I_p(Y; V|Z) \\ \Delta \geq E_p[d(X, Y)] \end{array} \right\},$$

where $D_D^{(j)}$ is defined as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_{X,Z,V,Y}: (X, Z) \sim p_{X,Z}, p_{Y,Z} = p_{X,Z}, \\ Z - X - V, X - (Z, V) - Y \\ I_p(Z; V) < \infty \end{array} \right\},$$

where the alphabet of V is constrained to be Polish.

There is a stark difference between Theorem 6 and Theorem 9: the entropy term in the former is absent from the latter. This highlights the fact that when a joint realism constraint is imposed, and the side information is available at both terminals, it loses its role as a source of independent common randomness.

2.1.3 Measuring semantic language mismatch between source and destination

In this section, we introduce how to tackle the language mismatch by meaning of measurable transformations within the semantic representation spaces.

Language and semantic space partition

A good language representation is instrumental in structuring the generation and consolidation of knowledge, influencing conceptual representation and semantic extraction and interpretation. A *Language generator* is a mapping function $\lambda: M \rightarrow X$, possibly parameterized, which endows a message or observation $m \in M$ of the world with semantic meaning $x \in X$. In the context of AI, a language generator defines a way to partition a semantic space and to associate to each partition a semantic meaning. For instance, let $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots\}$ be a partition of a probability space (X, \mathcal{B}, μ) , where μ is a probability measure over X , and \mathcal{B} is a σ -algebra² on X . A partition of X is often thought as a list of measurable sets that cover X . P_i is referred to as the i -th atom of the partition P . Thus, $\mu(P_i)$ is the probability measure of atom P_i .

Definition 1 [entropy of a partition]. The entropy of a partition $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_N\}$ is given by:

$$H_\mu(P) = - \sum_{i=1}^N \mu(P_i) \log(\mu(P_i)) \in [0, \infty],$$

The entropy $H_\mu(P)$ can be interpreted as a measure of the *a priori* uncertainty about the outcome of an experiment conduct in the partition P (experiment tells in which atom of the given partition the result is). If one of the partition's atoms has $\mu(P_i) = 1$, then there is no uncertainty about the outcome and $H_\mu(P) = 0$. If $\mu(P_i) = \frac{1}{N}$, $\forall i$, i.e. all atoms of the partition have equal probability measure, then the entropy is maximal.

An atom captures a certain level of semantics. For example, in an image classification task, an atom may be linked to the features (semantic symbols) associated with a certain class of images. Different languages may partition the semantic space differently. Similarly, different partitions of semantic space capture different levels of semantics. Depending on the meaning the sender assigns to each transmitted data m (i.e. the atom to which m belongs to), generated semantic symbols get interpreted by the receiver's language interpreter using a mapping function $\gamma: X \rightarrow A$.

Here, A defines the target message (interpretation) space, which may coincide with M , e.g. in image reconstruction task. However, it may also differ from M . For example, A may define the set of classes or actions associated with each message. Thus, $(M, \lambda, X, \gamma, A, \mu)$ fully characterizes a language. A good language is instrumental in structuring the construction and consolidation of knowledge, influencing conceptual representation, semantic extraction and interpretation. For communication to be effective, the sender and receiver must agree on a common or shared language, unambiguously interoperable. In other words, the receiver's language interpreter must be compatible with the sender's language generator. However, in practice, the sender and receiver may employ distinct languages (a different set of rules for representing and interpreting information). This is typically the case in distributed systems, where agents may employ different language models resulting from a local training procedure based on a privately maintained dataset. In addition, even if two AI agents are trained on the same data, they might not be able to "talk" to each other, in particular due to different training conditions (random weights initialization, training hyper-parameters, etc.), which entail different logic (internal representations) in learnt languages [MMF+22]. In such scenarios, [SC22] shows that communication is prone to semantic noise that might stimulate interpretation errors, causing defective co-operation strategies [WWP+20], which need to be circumvented.

² A σ -algebra on a set X is a nonempty collection of subsets of X closed under complement, countable unions and intersections.

An approximate measure of semantic language mismatch

In [SC23], we consider the general setting of a communication between two agents k and l , employing distinct languages $(M, \lambda_k, X, \gamma_k, A, \mu)$ and $(M, \lambda_l, X, \gamma_l, A, \mu)$ respectively. We assume $X \in \mathbb{R}^n$, i.e. the semantic representation space is a subset of a n -dimensional space. Let μ define a probability measure over (X, B) . Let $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_N\}$ and $Q = \{Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_N\}$ denote two finite partitions of N atoms³, defined by the agent's language generators λ_k and λ_l respectively.

Given a message $m \in M$, agent k encodes and transmits the associated semantic symbol $x = \lambda_k(m)$ to agent l , which interprets x in its own language as $\gamma_l(x) \in A$. However, in agent l language, data m gets mapped into $y = \lambda_l(m)$. Thus, agent l may misinterpret the received symbol x if $y \neq x$, i.e., if the target agent receives a different symbol from the one it would expect if the source agent adopted its language generator λ_l instead of λ_k .

However, since in our framework semantics are associated with partitions' atoms, it is not required to get $y = x$ to ensure correct interpretation at the receiver. Indeed, let P_i be the atom of the source partition to which x belongs to (i.e. $x \in P_i$) and Q_j the atom of the target partition to which y belongs to (i.e. $y \in Q_j$). Consequently, misinterpretation arises whenever $x \notin Q_j$. In this case, we say that the atom P_i is not aligned with the atom Q_j . In other words, they do not convey the same meaning w.r.t. the sender and receiver language. Put differently, the semantic channel between the sender and the receiver is not transparent (i.e. opaque). Hereafter, we propose to model semantic channel by a means of measurable transformations.

Definition 2 [Preimage of a set]. Let $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a transformation. The preimage of a set $Q \in X$ under one iterate of the transformation T , denoted $T^{-1}(Q)$, is defined as:

$$T^{-1}(Q) = \{x \in X \mid T(x) \in Q\}$$

The image of the preimage of Q is a subset of Q . That is $T(T^{-1}(Q)) \subseteq Q$. Equality holds if T is invertible.

Definition 3 [Measurable transformation]. Let (X, B) be a measurable space where B denotes a σ -algebra on X . A function $T: X \rightarrow X$ is said to be a measure transformation if $\forall B \in B, T^{-1}(B) \in B$.

A transformation can but does not need to be a translation, a rotation, or a permutation.

Quantifying semantic mismatch between the source and target language

Let T be a measurable transformation and \mathcal{T} denote the set of all possible transformations.

Figure 2-4 Semantic mismatch metric

³ In case they do not have the same number of atoms, one can always fill the partition having the lowest atoms with empty sets.

We introduce the following metric, operating at the language partitions level, to quantify the mismatch introduced by the semantic channel. Thus, $\forall (P_i, Q_j) \in P \times Q$, such that $\mu(P_i) > 0$, we define

$$\rho_{P_i \rightarrow Q_j}(T) = \frac{\mu(T^{-1}(Q_j) \cap P_i)}{\mu(P_i)}, \quad \forall T \in \mathcal{T}$$

Intuitively, following Figure 2-4, $\rho_{P_i \rightarrow Q_j}$ quantifies the fraction of the volume of P_i that ends up in the set Q_j under one iterate of the transformation T . Since μ is a probability measure, $\rho_{P_i \rightarrow Q_j}(T) \in [0,1]$ [SC23]. Thus $\rho_{P_i \rightarrow Q_j}(T)$ quantifies somehow the level of transparency (ranging from $[0,1]$ - full opacity to full transparency) of the semantic channel resulting from applying an arbitrary transformation T to align the atom P_i of the source partition to the corresponding atom Q_j in the target partition. Therefore, to align atom P_i with atom Q_j , it is sufficient to find a transformation $T \in \mathcal{T}$ that transports $x \in P_i$ into its equivalent semantic atom: $y = T(x) \in Q_j$

$$P1: T^* = \arg \max_{T \in \mathcal{T}} \rho_{P_i \rightarrow Q_j}(T)$$

Transformation T^* can be viewed as a language “*translator*” bridging the semantic gap between the source and target atom. Then, there exist different possible implementations of the transformation to recover exactly at the receiver the meaning intended by the transmitter:

- The receiver manages to invert the transformation introduced by the semantic channel (*post-equalization*),
- The transmitter intentionally distorts the intended meaning by sending another message (*pre-equalization*) or
- Both receiver and transmitter operate a transformation, which result in the overall transformation identified in (1) or in (2) (*hybrid-equalization*).

Identifying and implementing the right transformation is crucial for the communication performance.

2.2 Cost and performance in control, learning, optimization

In this section, we study “label-less” distributed machine learning settings, where the conventional assumption of consistently available ground-truth labels on resource-constrained devices is challenged. This assumption is commonly found in conventional distributed machine learning frameworks, such as federated learning [SC22, SDS+24].

One approach to address the absence of labels is to enable devices to request labels from an edge server while training local models, necessitating communication-efficient labelling protocols, which are connected to the active learning literature [RXC+22]. Another strategy involves leveraging SemCom to convey contextual information in the absence of ground-truth labels. For example, when devices only have access to unlabelled data, an edge server can specify the required content within a semantic space, as illustrated by the Semantic Data Sourcing (SEMDAS) framework proposed in [HLLY22]. This strategy also relates to data retrieval tasks in relational database systems that incorporate semantic understanding [CF80].

Along the contributions made in this section, we reveal trade-offs in cost and performance across control, learning, and optimization to achieve communication efficiency in these scenarios.

2.2.1 A Communication-efficient labelling protocol

Conventional active learning protocols aim to iteratively select the most informative data points for labelling in order to reduce interactions between a device and an edge server [RXC+22].

Recently, batch active learning methods have gained attention, as they allow for querying multiple data points at once rather than one per iteration. This approach reduces interaction even further and accelerates training, which is essential for deep learning models that require large datasets to get a meaningful training. However, most active learning protocols from pure machine learning literature focus on settings in which there are no explicit presence of communication channels between devices, referred to as *learners*, and edge servers, referred to as *teachers*. Moreover, these protocols often treat the teacher as an *oracle* capable of providing ground-truth labels for any unlabelled data. This arises from scenarios where teachers are domain experts who can label data accurately. In edge computing, however, the edge server is generally assumed to have access to pre-trained models that provide *weak supervision*, that is, high-quality but potentially noisy labels [SC22, SDS+24].

With the goal of studying a communication-efficient labelling protocol, we consider a batch active learning setting with weak supervision within a communication-theoretic framework, illustrated in Figure 2-5. We further explain it in the sequel.

Figure 2-5 A learner communicates with a teacher over a constrained communication channel to obtain soft labels for mixed-up batches of unlabeled inputs

We assume a setting in which a learner owns a small set of labelled data, L , is consistently collecting more and more data, yielding a pool set of unlabelled data, U , and owns a Bayesian model, M , with model parameters $\theta \sim p(\theta|L)$, where the conditioning in L expresses that the model was trained on L . Bayesian models leverage the bi-level representation machinery of Bayesian inference to introduce a prior distribution over the space of model parameters. As a result of this form of regularization, Bayesian models are robust to over-fitting, offer uncertainty quantification, and can more easily learn from small datasets. The learner can communicate with a teacher via a constrained communication channel. We assume that the constraint of the communication channel is in the form of a limited number of inputs that the learner can send, say $N > 0$. Different from the oracle assumption, we consider that the teacher is not a human but, for example, it is an edge server that stores another model, T , that is related to the task of interest to the learner, where the teacher’s model is better than the learner’s given a metric of interest. As the amount of labelled data is small on the learner’s side and the performance requirements for the task should be high, the learner wishes to acquire more labelled data to better train its model while keeping in mind communication constraints. To accomplish this, the learner applies an active learning approach by sending batches of unlabelled data to the teacher, denoted as $B = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_B\}$, to be labelled, where the batch size is $B > 0$. The teacher gives feedback to the learner based on the *knowledge distillation* technique [HVD15], that is, by using the soft labels from the output layer of its model.

For example, this scenario can be motivated by considering that the learner is a satellite running a personalized computer-vision model and the teacher represents an edge server with the required wireless communication capabilities that connects the satellite to the network and has access to pre-trained models. Notably, the communication window of a satellite is often very

limited and the data is often high-dimensional, requiring very high throughput capabilities. Therefore, we need to design communication-efficient protocols.

In conventional batch active learning, the learner would select a batch of inputs based on an acquisition function, which can be defined in view of a Bayesian perspective as follows [RXC+22]:

$$B^* = \arg \max_{B \subseteq \mathcal{U}} a(X, p(\theta|L)),$$

where $a(\cdot)$ is an acquisition function that scores candidate batches from the pool set and can be based on the current model parameters $p(\theta|L)$. In this conventional setting, the learner would send each input in the batch. Therefore, at each active learning iteration, it would consume B inputs out of N .

Our contribution was a communication-efficient protocol allowing the learner to request as much label information per interaction with the teacher as possible within an acceptable performance drop, named as *communication-constrained Bayesian active knowledge distillation* (CC-BAKD) [CPSP24]. Our key idea was to introduce a *batch encoding* module into the original active learning setting, reducing the number of inputs per batch by mixing them into a batch of smaller size B' with $B' \leq B$ such that only B' inputs are consumed per iteration. From a data compression point of view, this would mean that we are *mixing-up* the inputs of a batch. Furthermore, we employ a traditional encoder-decoder model, with the teacher possessing a decoder to decompress the mixed-up batch, where we also consider joint compression over both batch and feature dimensions. Thus, the compression ratio can be defined as:

$$R = \frac{BD - B'D}{BD},$$

where D is the number of features of an input x .

However, batch encoding adds noise to labels, impacting the learner's model quality. To mitigate this, we introduce two mechanisms: (i) a weighted learning criterion where weights reflect the learner's confidence in the soft labels provided by the teacher, and (ii) a generalized batch acquisition function operating in the compressed space. The latter was inspired by acquisition functions based on mutual information, such as in *batch Bayesian active learning by disagreement* (BatchBALD) [KAG19], where our approach extends mutual information acquisition functions to select batches that compress well together by leveraging statistical correlations.

Figure 2-6 illustrates that our protocol significantly accelerates label acquisition over traditional active learning protocols, while maintaining control over the impact of label noise on learning performance. Our setting considers the MNIST dataset of 28×28 greyscale images (see model and training details in [CPSP24]). As a proof-of-concept, we employ linear compression via principal component analysis. We note that communication efficiency requires additional computation, primarily for batch encoding/decoding and input selection within the compressed space.

Figure 2-6 A learner communicates with a teacher over a constrained communication channel to obtain soft labels for mixed-up batches of unlabelled inputs. Batch size is $B = 4$

Future research directions include investigating the relationship between batch encoding and semantic encoding methods. Additionally, we aim to address the “semantic mismatch problem” outlined in Section 2.1 in our setting, which arises when the learner and teacher operate in different semantic spaces.

A notable limitation of our protocol is the trade-off between communication efficiency and computational demands. The decision-making process occurring in the compressed space increases computational complexity, potentially leading to higher energy consumption. This trade-off requires further exploration to optimize energy efficiency without compromising communication performance.

More details can be found in [CPSP24].

2.2.2 Communication frameworks and related protocols based on semantic queries

Instead of depending on ground-truth labels, we can convey context through a semantic space. In [HLLY22], the authors introduced the SEMDAS framework, which utilizes the semantic space to identify devices as potential data sources for a given context. This approach enables *data retrieval* from these devices via semantic queries.

We now more formally define a semantic query and the basic functioning of the SEMDAS framework, focusing on a classification task. Let q be a semantic query vector in a semantic space, S , that captures the semantic of a data point x_q of interest. An edge server can use q to retrieve data from the devices that are related to a context defined by x_q by broadcasting q to them. The devices can then encode their data according to the shared semantic space, S , and score their data with respect to the semantic query, q . Essentially, a deep learning model is based on fitting a function $f : X \mapsto Y$ that predicts y from x , where X is the input space and Y is the output space. This function can be seen as a composite function $f = c \circ e$, where $e : X \mapsto S$ is the encoder component and $c : S \mapsto Y$ is the subsequent classifier. Let $g : (S, S) \mapsto \mathbb{R}_+$ be a matching score function. Based on the semantic space defined by e , a device can measure the relevance of their data with respect to the context defined by q as follows:

$$D_{\text{relevant}} = \{g(x, q) > t \mid \forall x \in D\},$$

where D is the dataset at the device and $t > 0$ is a threshold. The core principle behind semantic queries is the “*filtering out*” of irrelevant data, which can be referred to as *semantic matching*. Hence, from a statistical learning perspective, we can define the notions of positive and negative examples. A positive example refers to an instance x that genuinely aligns with the context defined by q , while a negative example denotes an instance that does not fit within this context.

However, a major limitation of semantic queries is that the shared semantic space must be well-defined, and the encoder function e should be known at the devices. In practice, the effectiveness of semantic spaces—and consequently, the quality of semantic queries—varies significantly with the specific task. This can lead to inefficiencies in protocols based on semantic queries, particularly when dealing with high-dimensional data or when the context captured by q is complex and dynamic.

In particular, we have studied two interrelated frameworks with associated protocols that leverage semantic queries for retrieving data from devices, which are detailed below.

Random Access Protocols Activated by Semantic Queries

We exploit the idea that filtering out irrelevant data can help to control the collision rate in a random access setting, where devices attempt to send their data to an edge server in an uncoordinated manner [KPG23]. In particular, we consider the setting in Figure 2-7, where multiple devices observe and collect data from specific events occurring in a certain environment, denoted by objects z_i . Some of the devices can have correlated data, as they observe the same object, forming a cluster. Our goal is to gain insights on how semantic queries can reduce uplink collisions in random access settings, thereby improving system throughput.

Figure 2-7 Random access activated by semantic queries. The figure depicts three phases: (1) a semantic query is broadcasted by the edge server; (2) the devices compute matching scores and filter out irrelevant data; and (3) the devices adopt a random access protocol and transmit their relevant data in an uncoordinated manner

We present a formal mathematical analysis to characterize how semantic queries can reduce collisions in a random access setting, focusing on two protocols: (i) the classical slotted ALOHA (SA) protocol and (ii) a correlation-aided slot-assigned ALOHA (SAA) protocol. The SAA protocol leverages semantic correlations to create coordination by having the edge server cluster devices and pre-assign specific slots to each cluster. Additionally, we employ an *attention mechanism* for semantic matching, decomposing a deep learning model into three components: a query encoder, a key encoder, and a classifier. Here, the classifier receives fused relevant data from devices, with the attention mechanism computing weights to prioritize contextually significant information.

An example of our findings is illustrated in Figure 2-8, which shows precision and recall under a Gaussian observation model for 100 devices grouped into 10 clusters, with each cluster observing the same object (see [KPG23] for further details). These assumptions simplify interpretation. Both random access protocols were evaluated with $L > 0$, representing the number of available slots. Here, the parameter δ controls the distribution of semantic matching scores, modelled explicitly as Gaussian in this basic setup, without using the attention-based semantic matching. Increasing δ polarizes the matching scores, improving the discrimination between positive and negative examples. The figure shows that leveraging correlations among devices enhances the prediction quality at the edge server while reducing collisions in the random access channel. It also reveals scaling laws on how semantic queries reduce the collision rate.

As future work, more extensive analysis to further understand the benefits of semantic queries in this setting is needed, which can be largely motivated by internet-of-things (IoT) application scenarios.

More details can be found in [KPG23]; there is an upcoming journal version of the manuscript with a more detailed analysis.

Figure 2-8 Precision and recall for classification at the edge server when considered two different random access protocols activated by semantic queries

EcoPull: Energy-Efficient Wireless Image Retrieval

As illustrated in Figure 2-9, we consider a wireless image retrieval setting with an edge server and $K > 0$ resource-constrained devices. Each device stores a local dataset of unlabelled images. The edge server wishes to retrieve or pull the images from the devices in an efficient manner. Our contribution is to propose a framework, called “EcoPull”, that does so while bearing in mind an integrated energy consumption evaluation over both computation and communication [TCSP24].

The framework considers that to save energy the devices communicate using semantics and is helped by two tiny machine learning (TinyML) models: a *behaviour model* and an *image compressor model*. Different from the random access setting above, the end goal of the EcoPull is to show the images collected from the devices to an end user instead of performing classification at the edge server. Our end goal with this framework is to reveal the energy costs related to enabling semantic matching at resource-constrained devices, which is related to evaluate the cost of inference of TinyML models over the devices and the cost of updating these models by transmitting them over a wireless channel when performance drops.

Figure 2-9 EcoPull, a sustainable IoT image retrieval framework in which two types of TinyML models are installed into IoT devices: i) a behaviour model and ii) an image compressor model

The mechanics of EcoPull can be described in four phases.

- Phase 1: the edge server broadcasts the semantic query, q .
- Phase 2: the devices receive this semantic query and use the behaviour model for semantic matching.

- Phase 3: The set of relevant images passes through the image compressor model, acting as a feature extractor, based on machine learning compression models, such as high-fidelity generative image compression (HiFiC) [TCSP24]. Notably, this model has outperformed conventional compression schemes, such as joint photographic experts groups (JPEG).
- Phase 4: The compressed set of relevant images is transmitted over a random access wireless channel using a slotted ALOHA protocol, where collisions are controlled via semantic matching. Finally, the edge server decompresses and shows the non-colliding relevant images to the end user.

We analyzed the performance-energy trade-off of this framework using an energy model that combines TinyML-based computation costs with communication-related consumption across all process phases. Additionally, we considered the need for the edge server to transmit the behaviour model and image compressor model to the devices due to their limited memory capacity and potential change of context.

Figure 2-10 illustrates energy efficiency as a function of the number of images per device, showing that TinyML models for semantic matching and compression are effective only when each device processes a sufficiently large dataset—at least around 30 images in this scenario (see simulation details in [TCSP24]). The main takeaway is that while filtering data based on semantic queries can save energy by reducing transmissions, it also incurs added computation energy consumption. This arises from using machine learning models for semantic filtering, which requires multiple forward-inference steps over data and periodic wireless model updates to adapt to the evolving context and task complexity.

More details can be found in [TCSP24].

Figure 2-10 Energy saving with respect to the Baseline scheme as a function of the number of images per device. We set the number of devices as $K=5$, the number of available slots as $L=5$, and the relevance threshold as $t=0.8$. The baseline scheme is comprised of traditional slotted ALOHA without semantic matching and using (portable network graphics) PNG for image compression

2.3 Management of semantic KB and model

2.3.1 Semantic KB definition

The semantic KB is a key element of a SemCom system, and it has been the focus of various studies in literature. The semantic KB is a structured repository of information that uses semantic technologies, such as ontologies and reasoning algorithms, to enable machines to understand, interpret, and infer relationships between data for more intelligent and context-aware decision-making. For the SemCom framework, KB offers a common understanding capability for the semantic encoder and decoder of the semantic tasks. In this subsection, we introduce our proposed distributed semantic KB system. To the best of our understanding, this is one of

the first studies on integration of a semantic KB wireless communication systems from both database and ML model perspectives.

2.3.1.1 Database-based KB

A distributed KB system is defined as a networked architecture where knowledge is stored, processed, and managed across multiple locations or nodes, allowing for decentralized access, scalability, and enhanced efficiency in decision-making and information sharing across diverse environments. By integrating semantic understanding across distributed environments, this system allows knowledge to be stored and processed across multiple nodes, enabling scalable management of vast amounts of data while reducing latency and bottlenecks in the entire system. In addition, these systems enhance the ability of inference and reasoning over complex, context-aware relationships, improving decision-making in dynamic and heterogeneous networks. Moreover, distributed semantic KB systems are more resilient and adaptable to changes in data sources, user requirements, or network conditions, providing greater flexibility for tasks like personalization service, real-time response, and network optimization. Overall, the distributed semantic KB system represents a transformative approach for modern networks, potentially transforming the traditional network into a knowledge-driven and semantic-aware network. It creates a robust framework that leverages semantic understanding to optimize resource allocation, enhance user experience, and drive intelligent, adaptive network behaviour across diverse and dynamic environments.

Particularly, we propose the multi-layer distributed semantic KB management system from the database operation perspective, including GKB, AKB, LKB, and UKB. In the following, we give the definitions and the architecture-level match of the distributed semantic KB and wireless communication system.

Figure 2-11 Architecture-level illustration of distributed KB in wireless communication systems

- GKB:** The GKB is a centralized knowledge repository located at the cloud data centre, as shown in Figure 2-11. It contains comprehensive, aggregated semantic information accessible across the entire network. This KB integrates data from various regional, local, and user KBs. Generally, GKB acts as the master source of semantic information, holding universal knowledge that can support inference, reasoning, and learning across different regions and users. It supports global tasks such as large-scale semantic analysis, policy setting, and high-level decision-making. The GKB is responsible for aggregating and storing knowledge from all connected LKBs in the network. In addition, it assists high-level semantic tasks like model training and large-scale semantic analysis.

Moreover, it works on distributing updates and high-level insights to regional and local KBs.

- **AKB:** The AKB is a region-specific knowledge repository located at the MEC server. It is responsible for handling knowledge specific to a geographic area or set of connected BSs. The AKB manages regional semantic information and performs mid-level tasks that benefit from low-latency edge processing, such as real-time optimization, network load balancing, and interference management within a specific region. Particularly, AKBs translate global policies from the GKB into regional adjustments and coordinate semantic tasks across multiple BSs or APs to optimize QoS and resource allocation. In addition, they aggregate data from LKBs and provide feedback to the GKB.
- **LKB:** The LKB is a localized knowledge repository situated at the BSs or APs. It provides cell-specific or small-area knowledge and supports low-latency, immediate-response tasks. LKBs perform local optimizations, user scheduling, and resource allocation within a specific cell or coverage area. They handle knowledge directly related to connected devices and adapt quickly to changing network conditions. The LKBs manage user-specific information and real-time semantic tasks, such as adapting transmission parameters based on user profiles and channel conditions. In addition, LKBs collect usage patterns and quality metrics to inform local adjustments and sending this data back to the AKB. They are also responsible for executing rapid semantic inference or content caching for frequently accessed data.
- **UKB:** The UKB is an individual knowledge repository located at the user's device (e.g., smartphones and IoT devices). It holds user-specific semantic information based on individual preferences, history, and usage patterns, which can vary due to the difference in knowledge levels. The UKB allows for personalized, user-centric semantic processing directly at the device level, supporting ultra-low latency for applications like content recommendation, personalized caching, and real-time adaptation to user preferences. One of UKB's functionalities is storing user-specific data, such as personal preferences, usage history, and localized content. Moreover, it adapts content and service quality based on device conditions, such as battery level and network connectivity. Additionally, UKBs provide personalized feedback to LKBs, supporting device-specific adjustments, and enabling predictive caching and content recommendations.

2.3.1.2 ML model-based KB

To enhance the efficiency and adaptability of distributed KBs, we introduce a ML-driven strategy for distributed KB management, as shown in Summary Table of KB Layers and ML Algorithms. Through ML-based methods, dynamic knowledge updating, context-aware retrieval, semantic compression, and inter-KB coordination can be achieved. This approach ensures that each KB remains up-to-date, relevant, and well-suited to the needs of diverse tasks and contexts within the network. In the following, we provide the ML algorithms for KB management at different layers.

- **GKB:** The ML models at the GKB level focus on high-level, long-term decision-making and include a semantic component to interpret and organize incoming data. They analyse historical and real-time data collected across the network to generate global policies, realize mobility and session management, and optimize network-wide performance. These models predict large-scale network trends, optimize resource allocation on a macro level, and create overarching policies that guide the behaviour of regional and local KBs. Particularly, GKBs integrate LLMs and self-supervised and federated learning for semantic GKB management. Firstly, the use of LLMs, such as GPT and BERT, is beneficial for GKB management because they are capable of handling large-scale, unstructured data, contextual knowledge integration, semantic understanding,

and policy generation. They help the GKB process complex, diverse information from AKBs and LKBs and translate it into global policies that can adapt to changing network conditions, making them highly effective in global knowledge management tasks. Secondly, federated learning aggregates renewals from multiple AKBs while preserving privacy, as only model updates instead of the source data are shared. Self-supervised learning is useful for building general representations of network semantics, such as identifying content patterns or predicting large-scale trends without human-labelled data and is therefore suitable for GKB management.

- **AKB:** ML models at the AKB level manage region-specific optimizations and real-time control with a semantic emphasis, focusing on load balancing, reducing interference, and optimizing QoS in specific regions. Here, ML models translate GKB policies into region-specific actions and manage adjustments based on real-time conditions, such as congestion and interference. Implementing both semi-supervised and reinforcement learning at the AKB level ensures knowledge from LKBs is high-quality and semantically aligned with real-time needs. On one side, semi-supervised learning is robust for edge-based scenario where only partial labelling is feasible. Labelled and unlabelled data are jointly leveraged to improve model accuracy. On the other side, reinforcement learning allows the AKB to optimize actions through trial and error, making it suitable for managing resource allocation, handling localized traffic congestion, and adapting policies from GKB for region-specific needs.
- **LKB:** At the LKB level, ML models operate at a low-latency, cell-specific level, focusing on real-time semantic updates and optimizations. LKB models ensure efficient, on-the-fly allocation of resources within the cell, influenced by immediate semantic context such as user scheduling and QoS. Compared with the tasks at AKBs, which focus more on translating global policies into specific regions, coordinating resources from a broader level, and aggregating and implementing strategies that have already been optimized elsewhere, the tasks at LKB raise higher demands on real-time adaptation and context-specific decision-making. Therefore, DRL is intended to be implemented for LKB management with large, continuous state-action spaces. Incremental learning further refines semantic models based on frequent user interactions, ensuring that the knowledge at the LKB is always current, accounting for the latest changes in user activity and channel conditions, enabling efficient handling of real-time tasks.
- **UKB:** The UKB contains personalized semantic knowledge specific to user preferences, behaviours, and contexts. Given the dynamic nature of user needs, UKB must be lightweight, adaptable, and capable of real-time adjustments. We propose using RLHF to semantically personalize UKB in real-time. This RL-based model can predict content or services a user might need next, caching locally to reduce latency, optimizing network usage based on battery status, and preemptively adjusting QoS based on user movement. By incorporating human feedback, RL continuously learns and adjusts to user-specific semantic patterns, allowing UKB to adapt as preferences evolve. Collaborative filtering is another effective approach to tailor content recommendations to users, which is realized by inference based on the preferences of similar users.

In summary, these ML algorithms play distinct roles at each KB layer, leveraging the specific characteristics of each location in the SemCom system. This layered approach ensures that each KB remains adaptive, efficient, and context-aware, enhancing the overall performance of the distributed KB system in SemCom.

KB Layer	ML/AI Algorithm	Characteristics	Application
GKB	LLM	Pre-trained on billions or even hundreds of billions of parameters; tuned for various downstream tasks with given prompts.	Manages high-level resource allocation, assists in inference and decision-making.
	Federated Learning	Distributed learning with sharing model parameters across data sources while preserving privacy.	Aggregates knowledge from AKB and LKB, creates global policies for resource allocation.
	Self-Supervised Learning	Learns patterns from unlabelled data, useful for large-scale semantic representation.	Builds generalized semantic patterns, assists in global semantic compression.
AKB	Semi-Supervised Learning	Uses labelled and unlabelled data, improves model accuracy in data-scarce environments.	Translates GKB policies, optimises for regional load balancing and manages local anomalies.
	Reinforcement Learning	Learns through trial and error with discrete and small state and action spaces, receives feedback from the environment in the form of rewards or penalties.	Manages resource allocation and traffic congestion at the regional level.
LKB	DRL	Learns optimal strategies through interaction with the environment; instructed to learn effective actions through rewards.	Manages user-specific scheduling, QoS, and interference handling in the cell.
	Incremental Learning	Updates model incrementally, adapting quickly to real-time data.	Adjusts to user and device interactions, keeps LKB current.
UKB	RLHF	Personalized, real-time adjustments based on user feedback.	Adapts content and caching to user needs, optimises QoS dynamically based on individual patterns.
	Collaborative Filtering	User preference-based recommendations, enhances personalized services.	Provides pre-caching and content recommendations, tailored for low-latency, user-specific needs

Table 2-1 Summary Table of KB Layers and ML Algorithms

2.3.2 Reinforcement learning-based methods for KB management

State-of-the-art works mainly focus on the model update, while ignoring the update and management of the KB. However, it should be noted that the mismatch between the model and the KB can lead to poor performance of the semantic models, due to the knowledge drift between the model's training domain and execution domain. Motivated by this fact, in this subsection,

we propose RL-based methods for KB management, which enable the dynamic adjustment and optimization of the information within the KB considering both its efficiency and its relevance.

2.3.2.1 Goals of KB Management at User Devices

In managing the KB at the UE side, the primary goals are to optimize for efficiency and relevance, as these metrics are fundamental to the effectiveness and practical value of the system in a real-world environment. On one side, KB utilization is used as the metric to evaluate communication efficiency. Specifically, KB utilization assesses the extent to which the KB's capacity is effectively leveraged, aiming to maximize useful content while minimizing unnecessary storage that could lead to latency or bottlenecks. By optimizing KB utilization, the system can maintain high performance without overloading communication channels or endpoint processing resources, ensuring efficient information flow and minimal latency. On the other side, relevance is determined by examining the cumulative usage frequency of all messages within the KB, which reflects the pertinence and usability of the stored knowledge for the endpoint's specific operational context. High relevance indicates that the KB contains valuable and frequently accessed information, increasing the likelihood that the endpoint will have the right knowledge at the right time. This metric helps in dynamically prioritizing content within the KB to adapt to changing contexts, user requirements, or network conditions. Thus, relevance supports the system's ability to retain pertinent knowledge that enhances decision-making, reduces unnecessary data handling, and aligns closely with the endpoint's functional goals.

We model the KB at the UE side as M , with its current and maximum utilization denoted as U and U_{\max} , respectively. To achieve efficiency and relevance, the KB must be updated adaptively. This involves uploading new and necessary information from other KBs and offloading uncorrelated or less frequently used information. We assume a message x is the symbol stream transmitted from other KBs, which is denoted as $x = C_{\delta}(S_{\gamma}(s))$. The semantic encoder network $S_{\gamma}(\cdot)$ is determined by parameter γ . The channel encoder $C_{\delta}(\cdot)$, with parameter set δ , is represented by dense layers with different input units. Then, after going through the AWGN channel, the symbol stream received by M can be expressed as

$$\hat{x} = x + n,$$

where $n \sim (0, \sigma^2)$. Correspondingly, the receiving side includes a channel decoder and a semantic decoder, which are used to recover the transmitted symbols and sentences, respectively. The decoded message can be expressed as $\hat{s} = C_{\delta}^{-1}(S_{\gamma}^{-1}(\hat{x}))$. A similarity score is used to determine whether this incoming message should be uploaded to M . Specifically, we calculate the similarity score between the incoming message and each message s_e in M as:

$$SS(s_e, \hat{s}) = \frac{B(s_e) \cdot B(\hat{s})^T}{\|B(s_e)\| \|B(\hat{s})\|}, \forall s_e \in M,$$

where $B(\cdot)$ represents a sentence transformer model that converts a sentence into a high-dimensional vector.

We model the KB management strategy from two perspectives, i.e., upload new messages and offload less-frequent used messages. Firstly, we define a threshold α to determine if the incoming message should be uploaded. If the maximum similarity score among all existing messages is smaller than α , indicating low similarity with existing messages in M , the incoming message will be uploaded; otherwise, it will not. Additionally, a threshold β is defined to trigger the offloading mechanism. When the KB size U exceeds $\beta \cdot U_{\max}$, offloading will be triggered, removing less frequently used messages to maintain $U \leq \beta \cdot U_{\max}$.

We formulate an optimization problem as follows:

$$\max_{\alpha, \beta} -w_1 U + w_2 \sum_{m \in M} \max\{f_{\min}, \min\{f_m, f_{\max}\}\}$$

$$\text{s. t.}, U \leq U_{\max}$$

$$\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]$$

where f_m denotes the usage frequency of message m , and f_{\min} and f_{\max} represent the minimum and maximum recorded usage frequencies, respectively. w_1 and w_2 are weights for the efficiency and relevance terms, respectively. The optimization of the thresholds α and β enables the dynamic and adaptive management of KB.

2.3.2.2 DRL-based KB Management Strategy

Based on the system model and optimization problem described above, the KB management process can be formulated as a standard MDP problem. To illustrate this problem, let us first define action, state, and reward.

- **State Space:** The RL agent must be able to assess the current state of the KB, the characteristics of incoming messages, and other key factors. The state space can include:
 - a. KB utilization U : The KB storage used. We define the initial size of M as U_0 , and the total/maximize size of the KB is $U_{\max} = \gamma U_0$, where $\gamma \geq 1$. The KB utilization U records the size of the utilized KB at each time and should always satisfy $U \leq U_{\max}$.
 - b. Usage frequency: The frequency with which existing concepts are being referenced. The frequency of all messages is varied under different time.
 - c. Current thresholds: The current value of α and β .

The state of the system at time t is denoted by $s_t = \{U_t, F_t, \alpha_t, \beta_t\}$, which denote the KB size utilization, usage frequency, and upload/offload threshold, respectively.

- **Action Space:**
 - a. Upload threshold α adjustment: Adjust the upload threshold upwards or downwards. α should be within the range of 0 and 1.
 - b. Offload threshold β adjustment: Adjust the offload threshold upwards or downwards. β should be within the range of 0 and 1.

We define A as the set for the action space at time t . $A_t \in A$ is a 1×2 vector, i.e., $A_t = [a_{\text{upload}}, a_{\text{offload}}]$. Note that the process of “inputting a message” and “calculating the similarity scores” would be part of the environment’s response (transition and reward generation), rather than the agent’s actions.

- **Reward System:** To reflect the performance of the action, we denote the immediate reward at time t as

$$r_t = -w_1 U_t + w_2 \sum_{m \in M} \max\{f_{\min}, \min\{f_{m,t}, f_{\max}\}\}.$$

Specifically, the first term is used to evaluate the efficiency of the KB, and the second term is used to track the relevance of the content in the KB at time t . A lower utilization size and a higher sum of usage frequencies indicate a higher reward.

The aim of the DRL is to find an optimal policy that achieves the maximum long-term reward from the state. Thus, we define the long-term reward as

$$R = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_i r_{t+i},$$

where $\epsilon_i \in [0,1]$ is the discount factor, which indicates the extent to which future rewards and immediate rewards affect the overall return.

2.2.2.3 DRL-based Model Training

In this subsection, we detail the DRL training process incorporating experience replay and a target network. Particularly, we use DQN, which is a specific DRL algorithm that approximates the Q-value function (used in Q-learning) in the Q-network, representing the expected cumulative reward an agent can achieve from taking a particular action in a given state and following a policy thereafter. Additionally, experience replay is used to overcome the typical drawbacks of the classical DQN algorithm [M19], shuffling sequences to eliminate correlations and allowing efficient reuse of experience to enhance data utilization. Specifically, it can first break up the sequence of transitions, eliminating correlations so that the data meets the criteria for independent and identically distributed samples, thereby reducing the variance of parameter updates and improving convergence speed. Secondly, it allows for the repeated use of experiences, which increases data efficiency. On the other hand, the target network is an additional copy of the Q-network used in deep Q-learning to stabilize the training process. When computing the target Q-values, the Q-values are not directly updated from the Q-network's latest parameters. Instead, they are updated from the target network, which holds a set of parameters θ' that are updated less frequently than the primary network's parameters θ . The set-up of the network target provides a more stable target and improves the convergence.

During the training process of the DQN, we first initialize both the primary Q-network Q_θ and the target Q-network $Q_{\theta'}$ with identical weights, setting up the experience replay buffer D with capacity N and other relevant parameters. For each episode, we initialize the environment state and conduct actions according to an ϵ -greedy policy based on the Q-network's predictions. With probability ϵ , a random action $a_t = (\alpha_t, \beta_t)$ will be selected; otherwise, the action that maximizes Q will be selected as:

$$a_t = \arg \max_a \{Q_\theta\}(s_t, a),$$

where s_t is the current state, including KB utilization, usage frequencies, and current thresholds. ϵ decreases over time to balance exploration and exploitation. After each action, we observe the subsequent state and reward and store the transition (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) in the experience replay buffer D . Once a sufficient number of experiences are stored, a mini-batch (s_j, a_j, r_j, s_{j+1}) is sampled randomly from the buffer. For each sample in the mini-batch, we calculate the target Q-value using the reward and the maximum predicted Q-value from the target network for the next state s_{j+1} , thus defining the target as

$$y_j = r_j + \gamma \max_{a_{j+1}} Q_{\text{target}}(s_{j+1}, a_{j+1}),$$

where γ is the discount factor. We then minimize the MSE loss $L(\theta)$ between the Q-values predicted by Q_θ and the target values y_j :

$$L(\theta) = \frac{1}{|B|} \sum_{j \in B} (y_j - Q_\theta(s_j, a_j))^2,$$

after which we update the policy network parameters θ using gradient descent:

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta - \eta \nabla_\theta L(\theta),$$

where η is the learning rate. Periodically, the target network is updated by copying the weights from the primary network in order to stabilize the training, as according to the following expression

$$\theta' \leftarrow \tau \theta + (1 - \tau) \theta',$$

where τ is a small constant (e.g., 0.01) to ensure a soft update.

Algorithm 2-1 demonstrates the complete DQN algorithm for the dynamic KB management. This process is repeated across episodes, and the Q-network learns an optimal policy by continually

improving its Q-value estimates through experience and target network guidance until convergence. In all, this process allows the DQN model to iteratively improve α and β values, enhancing the KB management's efficiency and relevance at the UE side by effectively balancing these two factors.

2.2.2.4 Numerical Results

In the simulation part, we use a MongoDB dataset for KB management, with documents divided into an existing KB (10%) and incoming messages (90%). The optimization problem is framed as an RL task where the two parameters, α and β , are adjusted continuously and dynamically within the range $[0, 1]$ to control upload and offload actions. The initial values for α and β are set at 0.5. Moreover, we set $w_1 = w_2 = 1$ and the number of steps in each episode to be 200. The usage frequency of each message in the KB varies between 0 and 1, which either increases or decreases in each step. The usage frequency of the incoming message is initialized as the average frequencies of existing messages.

Algorithm 2-1: DQN Algorithm for KB Management

1. Initialize experience replay buffer D with capacity N ;
2. Randomly initialize the weights θ of the evaluation network Q and the weights θ^- of the target network Q^- ;
3. For episode = 1 to M do
4. Select the initial state s_0 and pre-process the raw representation to obtain the feature representation $\phi_0 = \phi(s_0)$;
5. For $t = 1$ to T do
6. Select an action a_t using the ϵ -greedy policy;
7. Execute action a_t and observe the reward r_t and the next state s_{t+1} ;
8. Store the experience $(\phi_t, a_t, r_t, \phi_{t+1})$ in the experience buffer D ;
9. Sample a random mini-batch $(\phi_j, a_j, r_j, \phi_{j+1})$ from D and compute the TD target:

$$y_j = \begin{cases} r_j, & \text{if the episode terminates at step } t + 1 \\ r_j + \gamma \max_a Q^-(\phi_{j+1}, a; \theta^-), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$
10. Perform a gradient descent step on $(y_j - Q(\phi_j, a_j; \theta))^2$ to update the parameters of Q ;
11. If C steps have passed then
12. Copy the weights of Q to Q^- ;
13. End if
14. End for
15. End for

Algorithm 2-1 DQN Algorithm for KB Management

Figure 2-12 shows the successful convergence of the DRL method in the given numerical environment after approximately 40 episodes of training, which demonstrates the effectiveness of the trained network. In addition, we compare the optimized KB management strategy with two benchmarks, i.e., (a) random KB management policy, where α and β are randomly set in each step; (b) fixed KB management policy, where α and β are fixed as $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$. It can be seen

that the optimized KB management strategy could always realize the highest reward, ensuring relevance and efficiency of the KB.

Figure 2-12 The convergence behaviour of DRL-based KB management strategy (left side); Comparison of our proposed KB management policy with (a) random KB management policy; (b) fixed KB management policy (right side)

3 Approximation methods

This section is comprised of two subsections. In Subsection 3.1, we discuss approximation methods such as approximating semantic language translator via domain adaptation techniques and approximation techniques in image transmission over MIMO channels using DeepJSCC. In Subsection 3.2, we discuss topological data representation methods for semantic data extraction.

3.1 Definition and evaluation of approximate methods

3.1.1 Approximating semantic language translator using domain adaptation techniques

In this section, we are interested in approximating transformations introduced by the semantic channel between two users employing distinct languages. Our approach relies on optimal transport (OT) theory [OPV14]. We first introduce the original Monge-Kantorovitch problem and its discrete formulation. Then, we propose a new optimization framework, which relaxes the original problem constraints to learn approximated semantic language translators (i.e. transport maps).

Background on the Monge-Kantorovitch Problem

Let us consider communication between two users employing distinct languages, referred to as the source and target language, each partitioning the semantic space X into finite partitions $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{N_P}\}$ and $Q = \{Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_{N_Q}\}$ of size N_P and N_Q respectively. Hereafter, we assume $X \in \mathbb{C}^n$, where n is the dimension of the complex semantic space (each transmitted data is represented with n complex semantic symbols).

For any atom P_i of partition P and Q_j of partition Q , let $\mu_i \in P(P_i)$ and $\nu_j \in P(Q_j)$, where $P(A)$ denote the set of all probability measures over A . For any message m mapped to $x \in P_i$ by the source language, we seek a mapping $T: X \rightarrow X$, which transport x into the corresponding atom Q_j in the target language, i.e. such that $T(x) \in Q_j$. Specifically, we seek a transport map T that pushes μ_i onto ν_j , i.e. $T_{\#}\mu_i = \nu_j$, where $T_{\#}\mu_i$ is the image measure of μ_i by T , defined such that $T_{\#}\mu_i(A) = \mu_i(T^{-1}(A))$, $\forall A \subset X$.

Let $d: X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be a metric (e.g., a distance metric such as Euclidean distance). The optimal transport map, when it exists, can be found by solving the following Monge transportation problem:

$$\arg \min_T \int_{P_i} d(x, T(x)) d\mu_i(x), \quad \text{s.t. } T\#\mu_i = \nu_j$$

The existence of such map is not always guaranteed, e.g., when μ_i is supported on Dirac distributions and ν_j is not. To address this problem, the Kantorovitch relaxation seeks a general coupling $\gamma \in \Gamma_{i,j}$ between P_i and Q_j by solving the following problem:

$$\arg \min_{\gamma \in \Gamma_{i,j}} \int_{P_i \times Q_j} d(x, y) d\gamma(x, y)$$

where $\Gamma_{i,j}$ is the set of all probabilistic measures in $P_i \times Q_j$ with marginals μ_i and ν_j . In contrast to T , the optimal coupling exists but may not be unique [V09].

Case of discrete distributions. In practice, the exact distribution μ_i and ν_j is not known. Only a collection of samples $X_i = \{x_{i,k} \in P_i \mid k = 1, \dots, N_X\} \sim \mu_i$ and $Y_j = \{y_{j,k} \in Q_j \mid k = 1, \dots, N_Y\} \sim \nu_j$ of the source and target atom is available. In this case, the corresponding empirical distributions can be written as:

$$\mu_i = \sum_{k=1}^{N_X} p_{i,k} \delta_{x_{i,k}}, \quad \nu_j = \sum_{k=1}^{N_Y} q_{j,k} \delta_{y_{j,k}}$$

Here, δ_x denotes a unit point mass at the point $x \in X$, $p_{i,k}$ and $q_{j,k}$ are the probability masses associated to the k -th sample in X_i and Y_j , respectively, and belong to the probability simplex: $\sum_k p_{i,k} = 1$ and $\sum_k q_{j,k} = 1$.

Approximating language translator/semantic equalizer using Kantorovitch relaxation

As mentioned above, for each pair (i, j) of source and target atoms, we obtain the semantic equalizer $T_{i,j}$ by solving (P1): $T_{i,j} = \arg \max_{T \in \mathcal{T}} \rho_{P_i \rightarrow Q_j}(T)$. However, solving this problem is complex, in particular due to the difficulty to assess $\rho_{P_i \rightarrow Q_j}$. Therefore, we propose to cast problem (P1) into an OT problem, consisting in finding a mapping function to transport samples X_i of P_i to samples Y_j of Q_j .

Let $\Gamma_{i,j} = \{\gamma \in (\mathbb{R}^+)^{N_X \times N_Y} \mid \gamma^T \mathbf{1}_{N_Y} = \mu_i, \gamma^T \mathbf{1}_{N_X} = \nu_j\}$ be the set of probabilistic coupling between the two empirical distributions defined above such that $\mathbf{1}_N$ is the N -dimensional vectors of ones. In addition, let $D_{i,j} \in (\mathbb{R}^+)^{N_X \times N_Y}$ be the related matrix such that each entry $D_{i,j}[k, l] = d(x_{i,k}, y_{j,l})$. In [SC23], we show that when Euclidean distance is considered, problem (P1) can be casted into the following Monge-Kantorovitch problem:

$$P2: T_{i,j} = \arg \min_{T \in \mathcal{T}, \gamma \in \Gamma_{i,j}} \left[\|T(X_i) - N_X \gamma B_r(Y_j)\|_F^2 + \alpha \langle \gamma, D_{i,j} \rangle_F + \beta h(T) \right]$$

where α and β are some hyper-parameters; $h(T)$ is a regularization term, $\|\cdot\|_F$ and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_F$ are the Frobenius norm and dot product, respectively.

In problem (P2), $B_r(Y_j)$ denotes the *barycentric mapping*⁴ of the samples Y_j into a ball of radius centered in c , e.g., the centroid of the atom Q_j (see Figure 3-1). Thus, in contrast to [PCF+16], we seek a transport map that transports samples X_i from P_i into a ball contained in the convex hull of the samples Y_j , i.e. inside the atom Q_j (see Figure 3-1). This is because,

⁴ In the following, we define $B_r(Y_j) = c + r(Y_j - c)c = \mathbb{E}_{y \sim \nu_j}[Y_j]$, where $r \in [0, 1]$.

depending on the goal of the SemCom, perfect alignment between transported sampled $T(X_i)$ and Y_j could not be needed. What matters is that transported samples X_i fall inside Q_j (i.e., that $\rho_{P_i \rightarrow Q_j}(T) = 1$). The radius r of the ball controls the confidence at the RX in interpreting the meaning intended by the TX. It also robustifies transmitted semantic symbol against noise introduced by the syntactic/physical channel.

Problem (P2) can be efficiently solved using a block coordinate gradient descent approach as in [PCF+16].

Figure 3-1 Illustration of the barycentric mapping transporting X_i into a ball of the atom Q_j

Information transfer matrix

Let $\sigma(\cdot): J_P \rightarrow J_Q^{(5)}$ be a mapping function, which associates each atom $i \in J_P$ of P to the corresponding atom(s) $\sigma(i)$ in Q .

Remark: $\sigma(\cdot)$ is not required to be a one-to-one mapping. It can be many-to-one mapping i.e., many atoms from P can be mapped to only one atom of Q . For instance, in the aforementioned example, the digits $\{1, 3, 5, 7, 9\}$ are all odd numbers. It can also be a one-to-many mapping. In this case, $\sigma(i)$ is a set. For example, an even digit can be $\{0, 2, 4, 6, 8\}$. This case may ultimately lead to semantic ambiguity. For instance, it is not possible to recover exactly a digit knowing only its parity.

In the following, we restrict $\sigma(\cdot)$ to be a one-to-one or many-to-one mapping, then each atom i in P is associated to a unique atom j in Q . Accordingly, for each couple (i, j) such that $i \in J_P$ and $j = \sigma(i)$ we solve Problem (P2) to construct a codebook of transformations $C \subset T$. Thus, the size of the codebook is N_P . To identify the operational zone of the codebook, we define the following information transfer matrix $\rho \in [0,1]^{N_P \times N_P}$ such that $\rho[i, k] = \rho_{P_i \rightarrow Q_{\sigma(i)}}(T_k)$, $\forall i \in J_P$ and $T_k \in C$:

$$\rho = \begin{pmatrix} \rho_{P_1 \rightarrow Q_{\sigma(1)}}(T_1) & \cdots & \rho_{P_{N_P} \rightarrow Q_{\sigma(N_P)}}(T_1) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{P_1 \rightarrow Q_{\sigma(1)}}(T_{N_P}) & \cdots & \rho_{P_{N_P} \rightarrow Q_{\sigma(N_P)}}(T_{N_P}) \end{pmatrix}$$

In practice, we compute ρ offline via a Monte Carlo sampling, by applying each transformation to samples X_i and Y_j from $P_i \in P$ and $Q_j \in Q$ respectively.

Example

A sender observes the pixels value of random colour-MNIST image [FAdF+16], while the colour label (either red, green, blue, or yellow) and digit value are hidden, and encodes underlying information for a receiver, which infers the digit on the image or its parity. Here, the sender and

⁵ J_A denotes an index set of a partition A (i.e., A is labelled by means of elements of J_A).

the receiver have incompatible goals. The former encodes information in $N_P = 10$ possible options corresponding to the 10 digits, whereas the latter has $N_Q = 2$ possible options for decoding, corresponding to digit parity.

We use $N_Y = 5$, $N_X = 5000$ image samples and set $r = 1$ (default), $n = 2$, thus, encoding each colour image with only two complex semantic symbols. We assume language generators and interpreters are given, modelled as auto-encoders, and obtained after an end-to-end learning process, minimizing a cross-entropy loss as in [SC22]. In our example, language generators are composed of a convolutional layer of dimension $3n$, followed by a rectifier linear unit and a max-pool operator, another convolutional layer with dimension $8n$, followed by another max pooling operator, a dropout layer with probability 0.5, and a rectifier linear unit layer, whose output is flattened to feed a final linear layer of dimension $2n$. In contrast, each language interpreter only includes one linear layer of dimension $2n$. In addition, all convolutional layers use a kernel size equal to 5, and the max pool operators use a 2-sized kernel and stride. The power of the complex symbols x outputted by language generators is normalized so that $E[x] = 1$.

Figure 3-2 Information transfer matrix for different class of transformations

Figure 3-2 shows the information transfer matrix for different class of transformations/algorithms [PCF+16]:

- Sinkhorn algorithm (skh)
- Energy Mover’s distance (emd),
- Linear (linear)
- Gaussian kernel (gauss).

The x-axis corresponds to partition index (digit class label) and the y-axis to transformation index in the codebook. Recall that $\rho[i, k] = 1$ means that transformation T_k in the codebook is able to perfectly align atom P_i with the corresponding target atom $Q_{\sigma(i)}$. In other word, $\forall x \in P_i$, the RX is able to recover exactly the meaning if we use T_k to equalize the semantic channel. Hence, from Figure 3-2, we clearly see that depending on the class of transformations/algo-

rithms, each transformation has an operational zone. Moreover, we also see that the transformations in the related codebook can be redundant. There exist equivalent/orthogonal transformations, which motivates future investigations for minimal codebook design.

Now we want to assess the performance of the proposed strategy when a communication is set up between the sender and the receiver. To do so, we consider two benchmarks:

W/o Eq. (Without equalization): In this approach, we do not equalize the semantic channel. Communication undergoes as if the semantic channel is transparent. This is of course the worst-case scenario.

NN-based Eq. (NN-based equalization): Here, we model the transformation as a neural network (NN), which we train in an end-to-end fashion using the sender language generator together with the receiver language interpreter, whose weight are get frozen. This approach, common for adapting pre-trained models to a specific dataset, however, requires the knowledge of the dataset.

Proposed Eq. (Proposed solution): Here, we solve Problem (P2) for different ball radii focusing only on learning linear transformations. To do so, we assume a genie indicates which transformation in the codebook to select to compensate the language mismatch during communication. However, in WP4, we investigate dynamic approach for selecting transformations in the codebook based on stochastic optimization.

Figure 3-3 Performance comparison with different ball-radius and different value of SNR (physical channel)

As we can see from Figure 3-3, when no equalization is applied, the overall performance of the communication is 50%, which is what can be expected from a communication in which one has to guess the parity of a digit without any hint.

Overall, our proposed method clearly outperforms the benchmarked approach. In addition, decreasing the ball radius from 1 to 0.1 strengthens the communication against noise in the syntactic channel, resulting in the increase of the accuracy by 10%.

In conclusion, we have developed a novel approach to address the challenge of semantic channel equalization in multi-user SemCom, where senders and receivers use different languages. The proposed solution is robust against both syntactic and semantic channel noise, improving transmission accuracy with reduced complexity compared to traditional approaches. However,

handling a codebook of transformations comes with additional overhead, as it requires a strategy to dynamically select and apply the right transformation during communication. In future work we will investigate such selection strategies for effective SemCom.

3.1.2 Image transmission over MIMO channels using DeepJSCC

This subsection is interested in image transmission over multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) channels using the DeepJSCC approach [HSB+24]. We note that, while the optimal performance is already characterized by the RDP function through Shannon’s separation theorem. In practice, it is not possible to reach this bound in the finite blocklength regime. An alternative design approach has been pioneered through the utilization of neural networks with end-to-end optimization, called DeepJSCC [BKG19]. The pipeline of this scheme is described as follows: it first uses the JSCC encoder to encode the source image with extracted image features, and directly transmits them over a noisy MIMO channel, then uses the JSCC decoder to recover the source image at the receiver side. Two scenarios are considered, namely open-loop and closed-loop MIMO systems. In addition, based on different scenarios, we propose two different DeepJSCC-MIMO architectures. Then, we provide some simulation results to consolidate the superiority of the DeepJSCC-MIMO scheme and show that a good image reconstruction quality is achieved with limited bandwidth.

System model

As shown in Figure 3-4, the DeepJSCC MIMO architecture mainly consists of a JSCC encoder, precoder (depending on channel state information (CSI) availability at the transmitter side), MIMO channel, MIMO equalization, and JSCC decoder. We consider a MIMO system where both the transmitter and receiver are equipped with M antennas. The transmitter aims to deliver an image S to the receiver. The transmitter encodes the image S into a feature matrix $X \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times k}$. Then, X is transmitted to the receiver with the noisy distortion given by

$$Y = HX + W,$$

where H denotes the MIMO channel and W is the additive white Gaussian noise. In addition, the transmitter side should satisfy the power budget constraint:

$$\frac{1}{Mk} \|X\|_F^2 \leq P,$$

where P represents the transmit power.

Figure 3-4 Image transmission via DeepJSCC

Open-loop MIMO with CSIR

In an open-loop MIMO system, the channel state information (CSI) is only available at the receiver. The MIMO channel equalization should be performed before feeding the received signals to the JSCC decoder. In the following, the detailed steps of realizing open-loop MIMO with CSI at the receiver side (CSIR) systems are described as follows:

Let f_θ denote the encoder function with θ standing for the neural network parameters, which maps the source image S into the output X as follows:

$$X = f_\theta (S).$$

At the receiver, a MIMO equalization algorithm, namely a zero-forcing approach, is employed first to decode the transmitted feature signals based on the CSI:

$$\hat{X} = (H^H H)^{-1} H^H Y.$$

Then, a JSCC decoder, referred to as f_ϕ , is employed to reconstruct the source image based on the available CSI represented by the channel H and noise variance σ_w^2 , along with \hat{X} . This can be expressed as

$$\hat{S} = f_\phi (\hat{X}, H, \sigma_w^2).$$

Closed-loop MIMO with CSIT

In contrast to the open-loop MIMO with CSIR, the CSI is available to both the transmitter and receiver. In addition to the channel equalization on the receiver side, the precoding is performed on the transmitter. Specifically, given the CSI at the transmitter side (CSIT), we first decompose the channel matrix H by singular-value decomposition (SVD), yielding

$$H = U \Sigma V^H,$$

where U and V stands for unitary matrices and Σ is a diagonal matrix with the main diagonal elements representing singular values. Define Λ as the power allocation at the transmitter, where Λ is a diagonal matrix, with the diagonal elements being the power allocation, which can be adaptively learned based on the channel conditions. In addition, let V be the precoder at the transmitter. Furthermore, let U^H be the equalizer at the receiver. Then, by applying the precoder and equalizer, the noisy signal of \hat{X} can be expressed as

$$\hat{X} = X + \hat{W},$$

where $W = \Sigma^{-1} U^H W$ is the equivalent noise.

Therefore, by feeding \hat{X} into the JSCC decoder, the image can be recovered as

$$\hat{S} = f_\phi (\hat{X}, H, \sigma_w^2).$$

Proposed DeepJSCC-MIMO architecture

This subsection presents a pipeline of the DeepJSCC architecture to enable efficient image transmission in MIMO systems as shown in Figure 3-5.

In the following, we detail the pipeline of DeepJSCC-MIMO in five main steps: image-to-sequence transformation, channel heatmap construction, ViT encoding, ViT decoding, and the loss function.

Image-to-Sequence Transformation: To adapt the transformer architecture, we first convert the three-dimensional input image S into a sequence of vectors. Each S is divided into a grid of $p \times p$ patches.

Channel Heatmap Construction: To fully exploit all information and make the DeepJSCC model robust to the channel conditions, the channel heatmap is proposed, where the channel power gain is fed to both the DeepJSCC encoder and decoder. The channel heatmap denoted by P_n is given as follows:

$$P_n = \sigma_w^2 (H_w * \bar{H}_w) \quad \text{MIMO with CSIR,}$$

$$P_n = \sigma_w^2 \Sigma^{-1} U^H \quad \text{MIMO with CSIT,}$$

where \bar{H}_w denotes the element-wise conjugate of matrix of $H_w = (H^H H)^{-1} H^H$, and J represents the matrix with all elements being one.

Figure 3-5 The pipeline of the DeepJSCC-MIMO scheme

ViT encoding: The ViT encoding mainly consists of linear projection layers, a positional embedding layer, and several transformer layers as shown in Figure 3-6.

Figure 3-6 The architecture of the ViT-based encoder and decoder

ViT decoding: The ViT decoding is the inverse of the ViT encoding and mainly consists of a Siamese layer, positional embedding layer, transformer layer, and linear projection layer, similar to Figure 3-5.

Loss function: Although the MSE is typically adopted, a lower MSE doesn't indicate a good perception from humans. A more suitable evaluation metric for image reconstruction is the LPIPS, which better reflects the perception of humans. To this end, the loss function is defined as

$$L(\theta, \phi) = \text{MSE}(S, \hat{S}) + \lambda \times \text{LPIPS}(S, \hat{S}),$$

where λ is the hyperparameter.

Representative example

In the following, the simulation results are provided. We consider a 2×2 MIMO system and the CIFAR10 dataset, which has 50000 images with dimensions $3 \times 32 \times 32$ as the training dataset and 10000 images as the test dataset.

Evaluation of CSIR

The following benchmark schemes are considered:

- BPG-Capacity: the capacity-achieving channel codes for transmission is considered.
- BPG-LDPC: BPG codec + LDPC are considered.
- DeepJSCC-MIMO-universal: a random SNR is adopted at the training stage while testing at a specific SNR.
- DeepJSCC-MIMO: training and testing use the same SNR.

Figure 3-7 PSNR and LPIPS versus SRNs under bandwidth ratios

Figure 3-7 shows the PSNR performance obtained by the DeepJSCC-MIMO-universal, DeepJSCC-MIMO, BPG-Capacity, and BPG-LDPC schemes over the SNR under different bandwidth ratios. It can be observed that the DeepJSCC-MIMO scheme can generally outperform the BPG-Capacity and BPG-LDPC schemes in all SNR values. Note that the BPG-Capacity performance is not achievable by practical channel coding schemes. Thus, it serves as an upper bound on any separation-based scheme that employs BPG for compression of the input image. In addition, we observe that the gap between DeepJSCC-MIMO and BPG capacity is larger in the lower bandwidth ratio case. In addition, it can readily be seen that DeepJSCC-MIMO achieves the best perceptual performance across a range of channel conditions and bandwidth ratios. Last but not least, the DeepJSCC-MIMO-universal achieves comparable performance to the DeepJSCC-MIMO, which indicates the SNR-adaptability of the proposed scheme.

Evaluation of CSIT

In Figure 3-8, we visualize the results of the DeepJSCC-MIMO scheme on the Kadak dataset and compare them with those of the BPG-Capacity scheme. It can be observed that DeepJSCC-MIMO performs better in the low SNR regime, such as 1 and 5 dB, with more detailed high-frequency features. Comparing the performance of DeepJSCC-MIMO-universal and DeepJSCC-MIMO schemes, one can observe that the DeepJSCC-MIMO-universal can achieve comparable performance at the expense of a slight drop in distortion.

3.2 Topological data representation and semantic extraction

A key challenge in SemCom lies in balancing the complexity of data representation with the importance of transmitted symbols to effectively convey intended meanings or semantics, while maintaining acceptable levels of distortion or perceptual variation [GZQ+22]. Achieving this balance requires robust techniques to model, extract, and encode the semantics of data. In a very general sense, semantics can be conceptualized as the relationships between different parts of data or, even more broadly defined, the relations between the elements of a language. These relationships can be formalized using topological spaces—mathematical structures comprising elements and their interconnections [S89].

A fundamental example of a topological space is a graph, which represents pairwise or dyadic relationships (edges) between objects (vertices). Despite their simplicity, graphs serve as powerful tools for modelling knowledge and complex systems across disciplines such as biology, physics, computer science, and engineering. In Natural Language Processing (NLP), for example, graphs are pivotal for associating meanings with sentences and resolving ambiguities. Advances like contextualized word embeddings derived from large language models have revolutionized tasks such as text generation, sentiment analysis, and machine translation. Investigating the topological properties of these embeddings can reveal deeper insights into the structures underpinning NLP models, thereby advancing language processing technologies. Similarly, in computer vision, graphs are employed to represent semantic relationships by clustering image regions belonging to the same object class or recognizing 3D object shapes.

Figure 3-8 Visual comparison of different schemes on two samples from the Kodak dataset at a bandwidth ratio $R = 1/24$ and different SNRs

However, while graphs are versatile, they are inherently limited to capturing pairwise relationships. Many real-world scenarios involve higher-order (multiway) relationships that provide richer and more informative connections. For instance, in image segmentation, analysing texture homogeneity necessitates evaluating groups of pixels rather than pairs, as pairwise relations alone cannot fully capture texture similarities. To address such scenarios, higher-order networks such as hypergraphs offer a more appropriate framework. Furthermore, specialized forms of hypergraphs, such as simplicial and cell complexes, provide an algebraic foundation for encoding complex topological information. Examples include combinatorial complexes and cellular sheaves [PBB+24]. Once the relevant set of multiway semantic relationships is determined, data can be modelled as signals over a topological space. In this context, topological signal processing (TSP) becomes a fundamental tool for semantic data representation and communication [BCG+23]. The choice of topological space is critical, as it directly affects the ability to process data and achieve an efficient, parsimonious representation that optimally balances accuracy and complexity. In the sequel, we first introduce some fundamental tools from algebraic topology and TSP; then, we will introduce an algorithmic framework for semantic data representation and compression based on a methodology that learns dictionaries for sparse representations of topological data.

3.2.1 Semantic data representation and processing via topological spaces

In this section, we introduce signals over topological spaces; in particular signals over simplicial and cell complexes, along with the algebraic description of the associated topological domain encoding semantic relationships. To ease exposition, we start from signals defined over graphs.

Let us consider a graph $G = (V, E)$ consisting of a set of N nodes $V = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, along with a set of edges $E \subset V \times V$. Let us also denote the $N \times N$ adjacency matrix as A where the element (i, j) is denoted as $A_{i,j}$, $i, j \in V$. We assume $A_{i,j} > 0$, if there is a link from node j to node i , i.e., $(j, i) \in E$, or $A_{i,j} = 0$, otherwise. The combinatorial Laplacian matrix for an undirected graph with a symmetric adjacency matrix A is defined as $L = \text{diag}(1^T A) - A$. A signal x over a graph G is defined as a mapping from the vertex set to the set of real numbers, i.e., $x : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Here, entry x_i is the signal value associated to node $i \in V$. Clearly, this definition can be generalized by associating vector or matrix-type data to nodes. The assumption is that the algebraic proximities between nodes encoded in A or L translate into semantic relationships between the respective signals. Such a coupling can then be used for processing signal x by relying on neighbouring semantic information in a similar way as we process temporal and image signals based on temporal or spatial proximities.

Graphs can model only pairwise semantic relationships. Thus, in the sequel, we introduce higher-order network domains that incorporate multi-way semantic relationships in the data. These relationships can be represented using hypergraphs or complexes, as depicted in Figure 3-9. In the sequel, we will focus our attention to simplicial or cellular complexes, which serve as well-structured and algebraically rich generalizations of hypergraphs. We will keep the description as simple as possible, yet rigorous. Further details can be found in [ILB+24].

Figure 3-9 Examples of topological spaces for semantic data representation [HZP+22]

Simplicial Complex. Given a finite set of vertices V , a k -simplex $H_{k,i}$ is a subset of V with cardinality $k + 1$. A face of $H_{k,i}$ is a subset with cardinality k and thus a k -simplex has $k + 1$ faces. A coface of $H_{k,i}$ is a $(k + 1)$ -simplex that includes $H_{k,i}$. If two simplices share a common face, then they are lower neighbours; if they share a common coface, they are upper neighbours. A simplicial complex X_K of order K , is a collection of k -simplices $H_{k,i}$, $k = 0, \dots, K$ such that, if a simplex $H_{k,i}$ belongs to X_K , then all its subsets $H_{k-1,i} \subset H_{k,i}$ also belong to X_K (inclusivity property). In most of the cases the focus is on complexes of order up to two X_2 , thus having a set of vertices V with $|V| = V$, a set of edges E with $|E| = E$, and a set of triangles T with $|T| = T$.

Cellular Complexes allow for more general type of relations in the data, avoiding the inclusion property assumption. As an example, a cellular complex of order 2 can also define polygon type of relations among the data (e.g., squares, pentagrams, etc.).

Simplicial signals. A k -simplicial signal is defined as a collection of mappings from the set of all k -simplices contained in the complex to real numbers:

$$\mathbf{x}_k = [x_k(\mathcal{H}_k, 1), \dots, x_k(\mathcal{H}_k, i), \dots, x_k(\mathcal{H}_k, N_k)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{N_k}$$

For second-order SCs, the k -simplicial signals are defined as the following mappings:

$$\mathbf{x}_0 : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad \mathbf{x}_1 : E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad \mathbf{x}_2 : T \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

representing graph, edge and triangle signals, respectively. In this case, the corresponding SC signal is given by

$$\mathcal{X} = [\mathbf{x}_0 \parallel \mathbf{x}_1 \parallel \mathbf{x}_2] \in \mathbb{R}^{N+E+T}$$

Algebraic representation. The structure of a simplicial complex is fully described by the set of its incidence matrices \mathbf{B}_k , $k = 1, \dots, K$. The entries of the incidence matrix \mathbf{B}_k establish which k -simplices are incident to which $(k-1)$ -simplices. We use the notation $\mathcal{H}_{k-1, i} \sim \mathcal{H}_{k, j}$ to indicate two simplices with the same orientation. The entries of \mathbf{B}_k are defined as:

$$[\mathbf{B}_k]_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \mathcal{H}_{k-1, i} \not\subset \mathcal{H}_{k, j} \\ 1, & \text{if } \mathcal{H}_{k-1, i} \subset \mathcal{H}_{k, j} \text{ and } \mathcal{H}_{k-1, i} \sim \mathcal{H}_{k, j} \\ -1, & \text{if } \mathcal{H}_{k-1, i} \subset \mathcal{H}_{k, j} \text{ and } \mathcal{H}_{k-1, i} \not\sim \mathcal{H}_{k, j} \end{cases}$$

As an example, considering a simplicial complex X_2 of order two, we have two incidence matrices: the node-to-edge incidence matrix $\mathbf{B}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{V \times E}$, and the edge-to-triangle incidence matrix $\mathbf{B}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{E \times T}$. From the incidence information, we can build the higher-order Hodge Laplacian matrices, of order $k = 0, \dots, K$, as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{L}_0 &= \mathbf{B}_1 \mathbf{B}_1^T \\ \mathbf{L}_k &= \mathbf{B}_k^T \mathbf{B}_k + \mathbf{B}_{k+1} \mathbf{B}_{k+1}^T = \mathbf{L}_k^{(d)} + \mathbf{L}_k^{(u)}, \quad k = 1, \dots, K-1 \\ \mathbf{L}_K &= \mathbf{B}_K^T \mathbf{B}_K \end{aligned}$$

Here, \mathbf{L}_0 is with the combinatorial graph Laplacian and captures node-to-node proximities. All Laplacian matrices of intermediate order, i.e. $k = 1, \dots, K-1$, contain two terms: The first term also known as lower Laplacian, encodes the lower adjacency of k -order simplices; the second term, also known as upper Laplacian, encodes the upper adjacency of k -order simplices. Thus, for example, two edges are lower adjacent if they share a common vertex, whereas they are upper adjacent if they are faces of a common triangle.

Spectral representation and filtering. Hodge Laplacians of order k enjoys an eigendecomposition of the form

$$\mathbf{L}_k = \mathbf{L}_k^{(d)} + \mathbf{L}_k^{(u)} = \mathbf{B}_k^T \mathbf{B}_k + \mathbf{B}_{k+1} \mathbf{B}_{k+1}^T = \mathbf{U}_k \mathbf{\Lambda}_k \mathbf{U}_k^T$$

with orthogonal eigenvector matrix \mathbf{U}_k and eigenvalue matrix $\mathbf{\Lambda}_k$. Then, the *topological Fourier transform* (TFT) of a signal \mathbf{x}_k is given by the projection onto the eigenvectors \mathbf{U}_k , i.e.,

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k = \mathbf{U}_k^T \mathbf{x}_k$$

The i -th entry of the TFT represents the weight of the i -th eigenvector in expressing signal.

The inverse TFT is given by

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{U}_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$$

Spectral filtering of topological signal can then be applied directly to the transformed representation $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$. However, this approach is computationally expensive as we need to compute the eigendecomposition of the Hodge Laplacian matrices. To avoid the latter, topological convolutional filters can be designed to process the k -th signal \mathbf{x}_k and produce the output \mathbf{y}_k as:

$$\mathbf{y}_k := \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{L}_k) \mathbf{x}_k := \underbrace{\sum_{t=0}^{T_d} h_{kt}^{(d)} (\mathbf{L}_k^{(d)})^t \mathbf{x}_k}_{\mathbf{H}_k(\mathbf{L}_k^{(d)})} + \underbrace{\sum_{t=0}^{T_u} h_{kt}^{(u)} (\mathbf{L}_k^{(u)})^t \mathbf{x}_k}_{\mathbf{H}_k(\mathbf{L}_k^{(u)})}$$

where $h_{kt}^{(d)}$ and $h_{kt}^{(u)}$ are the filter parameters associated to the lower and upper Hodge Laplacians, respectively. As for the convolutional filters in time and images, the operation builds upon the shift-and-sum principle by propagating signal to neighbouring simplices via either the upper or lower adjacencies.

3.2.2 Semantic data compression based on topological dictionary learning

In this section, hinging on formal arguments from algebraic topology and TSP, we introduce a novel class of learnable dictionaries for topological signals, which enable to find compact (sparse) representations of data that incorporate the semantic structure. Specifically, we build the dictionary as the concatenation of P sub-dictionaries parametrized as polynomials of the Hodge Laplacians, i.e., $\mathbf{D} = \{\mathbf{D}_1, \mathbf{D}_2, \dots, \mathbf{D}_P\} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times PM}$, where each sub-dictionary is given by a convolutional topological filter $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{L}_k)$ parametrised by a vector coefficient \mathbf{h}_k for $k=1, \dots, P$.

This dictionary is a collection of P sub-dictionaries and is parametrized by all filters coefficients, denoted as $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{R}^{(2J+1)P}$. Also, we do not assume to have full knowledge of the topological domain. In particular, we assume that only pairwise relationships in the data are known (i.e., the graph representing the 1-order skeleton of the complex), and we aim to infer the higher order relationships from data. Let $\mathbf{t} \in [0, 1]^T$ be the indicator vector denoting which triangles (or polygons) are filled (if $t_i = 1$), and which are not (if $t_i = 0$). Overall, the dictionary is a function of both the filter parameters \mathbf{h} and the topological indicator vector \mathbf{t} , i.e., $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{h}, \mathbf{t})$.

We are now in the condition of formulating the dictionary learning problem. Given a training set of N k -topological signals $\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$, we aim to learn an overcomplete dictionary \mathbf{D} , which can represent the training signals as a sparse linear combination of the atoms. Thus, we formulate the dictionary learning problem as a joint optimization w.r.t. the dictionary coefficients \mathbf{h} , the sparse signal representation \mathbf{X} , and the topological indicator vector \mathbf{t} , as [GBR+24].:

$$\underset{\mathbf{h}, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{t}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{h}, \mathbf{t})\mathbf{X}\|_F^2 + \gamma \|\mathbf{h}\|_2^2$$

subject to

$$(a) \|\mathbf{x}_i\|_0 \leq K_0, \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

$$(b) 0 \preceq \mathbf{D}_p \preceq d\mathbf{I}, \quad p = 1, \dots, P$$

$$(c) (d - \varepsilon)\mathbf{I} \preceq \sum_{p=1}^P \mathbf{D}_p \preceq (d - \varepsilon)\mathbf{I}, \quad p = 1, \dots, P$$

$$(d) \mathbf{t} \in \{0, 1\}^P$$

where constraint a) enforces sparsity of the data representation; and b)-c) impose a desired structure of the dictionary (to enforce tightness of the resulting frame). The optimization problem above is non-convex and it is difficult to handle given the simultaneous optimization w.r.t. three different variables. We can approximate its solution with a more efficient iterative alternating-direction optimization algorithm for the \mathbf{h} and \mathbf{X} variables, and a greedy search for the optimal vector \mathbf{t} . In a first step, we consider the upper Laplacian parameters \mathbf{t} as fixed (e.g., to the full topology), and then setup an alternating-direction procedure where we optimize only with respect to one of the other two variables at each iteration, deriving two distinguished, easier sub-problems. At convergence, we remove the triangle (or polygon) leading to the largest decrease of the approximation error, and repeat again the alternating optimization strategy. We keep doing this procedure until there is no more incentive in removing other triangles from the topology. All the implementations' details are explained in [GBR+24].

Numerical results. We first test our proposal on synthetic data. To generate the datasets, we assumed a topology given by a simplicial complex, which was structured with 40 nodes, 100 edges, and a maximum number of 62 triangles. Then, we generated data according to the pro-

posed dictionary model (named as Separated Hodge Laplacian), concatenating 3 sub-dictionaries, each of them being an order 3 polynomial ($P = 3, J = 3$). Training and test sets are generated by linearly combining random atoms (at maximum 20) from the dictionaries with random coefficients. In Figure 3-10, we compare the behaviour of the test normalized mean-squared error (NMSE) versus the number of coefficients used to represent signals, for different dictionary constructions: (i) topological Fourier; (ii) Edge Laplacian, which takes into account only pairwise relations in the data; (iii) Joint Hodge Laplacian, which does not discriminate filtering between upper and lower topological domains. As we can notice from Figure 3-10, the proposed Separated Hodge Laplacian approach shows the best performance and generalization capabilities with respect to all the considered strategies. to all other competitors, especially in the case where topology is learnt jointly with the dictionary structure.

Figure 3-10 NMSE versus representation coefficients, for different strategies

In Figure 3-11, we illustrate an example of topology learning of the proposed methodology. We assume the topology illustrated on the left side of the figure, with 31 filled triangles (i.e., the 50% of all the possible triangles). Then, we generate synthetic data according to the same previous model, assuming a sparsity level equal to 9. Then, in the centre and right of Figure 3-11, we illustrate the result of our topology inference method, according to two greedy strategies named optimistic (since it starts removing triangles from the full topology) and pessimistic (since it starts adding triangles assuming an initial empty topology). As we can see from Figure 3-11, both strategies enable an excellent estimate of the underlying relationships among data, leading to a reconstruction NMSE that is very close to the optimal one achieved with a priori knowledge of the topological structure.

Finally, we apply the proposed method on real traffic data over the German National Research and Education Network (DFN), represented as the 1-skeleton of the underlying topology. The dataset consists of daily aggregated traffic measurements from February 2005, expressed in Mbit/sec and collected across each link in the network. The comparison done in Figure 3-12 highlights the accuracy-compression trade-off of various methods, including topological Fourier, topological Slepian, and Hodgelets. Among these, the proposed topological dictionary learning demonstrates superior performance, achieving the most accurate, compact representation of the traffic patterns. This result further demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed topological dictionary learning methodology in capturing the intricate semantic structures within the data and performing efficient compression.

Figure 3-11 Example of Semantic Topological Learning

Figure 3-12 NMSE versus representation coefficients, for different compression strategies

4 Conclusion

This deliverable has provided foundational insights into the mathematical and theoretical aspects of goal-oriented SemCom networks in the context of 6G systems. By extending traditional information-theoretic frameworks, this work has introduced metrics and methodologies that emphasize semantic content, contextual relevance, and perceptual quality in communication processes. The development of the RDP framework, alongside the application of α -divergences and measurable transformations, represents significant strides in quantifying and optimizing semantic interactions. We have then extended this framework to the transmission of images over a wireless channel, where the Shannon theoretic limits prescribed by the RDP trade-off cannot be achieved. We have proposed an alternative joint design approach benefitting from deep neural networks to approximate the optimal performance in practice.

Key contributions included novel approaches to addressing semantic mismatches, efficient KB management, and communication-efficient labelling protocols for distributed learning systems. Practical advancements, such as deep learning-based compression methods and domain adaptation techniques, further demonstrate the applicability of these theoretical developments in real-world scenarios. These results lay the groundwork for building intelligent, context-aware systems that prioritize the utility and meaning of transmitted information, moving beyond traditional notions of data fidelity.

Future Directions

While this deliverable establishes a strong theoretical foundation, several critical challenges could be addressed to fully realize the vision of 6G goal-oriented SemCom networks:

1. **Real-Time Implementation and Scalability:** Future work must focus on translating the proposed frameworks into real-time systems capable of operating at scale. This includes optimizing algorithms to handle the high-dimensional and dynamic nature of semantic data in real-world applications.
2. **Energy Efficiency and Sustainability:** The trade-offs between computational demands, energy consumption, and communication efficiency require further exploration. Developing energy-efficient protocols and hardware solutions will be pivotal for sustainable deployment.
3. **Interoperability and Semantic Alignment:** Addressing semantic mismatches between diverse systems remains a pressing challenge. Future research should explore adaptive techniques for achieving interoperability, particularly in heterogeneous and distributed environments.
4. **Enhanced KB Management:** Expanding on reinforcement learning-based strategies, future studies should investigate hybrid approaches that integrate symbolic reasoning and machine learning to enhance the scalability and robustness of distributed KBs.
5. **Integration with Emerging Technologies:** The interplay between SemCom and emerging technologies such as edge computing, blockchain, and quantum communication offers exciting opportunities. Exploring these synergies can unlock new capabilities for intelligent, secure, and context-aware systems.
6. **Exploration of Novel Use Cases:** Expanding the theoretical frameworks to address domain-specific applications, such as healthcare, autonomous systems, and industrial IoT, will be essential for demonstrating the practical utility of SemCom.

In conclusion, this deliverable sets the stage for transformative advancements in 6G communication networks, emphasizing the integration of semantics and goal-oriented optimization. Continued interdisciplinary research and collaboration will be critical to overcoming the remaining challenges and realizing the full potential of these innovative concepts.

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